

Scheduling in Unit-Aware, Batch-Constrained Job Shops

Evaluation of Dispatching Rule Strategies and Simulated Annealing Approaches

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Declaration of Authorship

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I hereby declare that except where specific reference is made to the work of others, the contents of this thesis are original and have not been submitted in whole or in part to obtain a degree or any other qualification neither in this nor in any other university. This dissertation is my own work and contains nothing which is the outcome of work done in collaboration with others, except as specified in the text. No other resources apart from the references and auxiliary means indicated in the bibliography were used in the development of the presented work.

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Abstract

Efficient scheduling in flexible, dynamic manufacturing systems is essential to ensuring timely production and optimal resource utilization. This thesis investigates the **Dynamic Flexible Assembly Job Shop Scheduling Problem with Batch-based execution**—a complex variant of classical job shop scheduling characterized by hierarchical product structures, batch-based execution, unit-level dependencies, and dynamic customer order arrivals. A particular focus is placed on realistic constraints such as setup times, resource capabilities, and multi-level dependencies, as exemplified in the real-world production of Radio-frequency Identification ([RFID](#)) tags.

To address this challenge, a discrete-event simulation framework is developed, capable of modeling dynamic order streams, batch constraints, and hierarchical assembly flows. The core of the scheduling logic is a configurable dispatching system that supports various heuristics—including First-In-First-Out ([FIFO](#)), Due Date, and Minimize Setup strategies—as well as their combinations via sequential and weighted formulations. Performance is evaluated using key metrics such as **Total Overdue Time**, **Total Priority Violation**, and **Total Setup Time**. To benchmark the heuristic approaches, the metaheuristic Simulated Annealing ([SA](#)) is implemented and analyzed.

Empirical results demonstrate that well-designed dispatching rules—especially when combined—offer robust performance at low computational cost and are well-suited to real-time scheduling scenarios. While SA offers theoretical improvements, its effectiveness is limited in this domain due to the intricacies of unit dependencies and batch execution. The findings underscore the value of heuristic-based scheduling in dynamic assembly job shops and provide practical insights for industrial scheduling systems.

The methods are validated using both real and synthetic datasets, with the real-world case study based on an RFID production process from one of SYSTEMA’s manufacturing partners. The approach and insights presented are applicable to a broader class of complex production systems beyond RFID, including semiconductor, electronics, and customized assembly lines.

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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
ASP	Answer Set Programming
BOM	Bill of Materials
DR	Dispatching Rule
EDD	Earliest Due Date
FIFO	First-In-First-Out
JSSP	Job Shop Scheduling Problem
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
RFID	Radio-frequency Identification
SA	Simulated Annealing
SPT	Shortest Processing Time
UPH	units per hour

Chapter I Introduction

In modern manufacturing systems, the efficient coordination of production resources—such as machines, materials, labor, and time—is a fundamental requirement for achieving high throughput, low lead times, and on-time delivery. As market demands for flexibility, customization, and responsiveness increase, manufacturers face rising complexity in how production is planned, scheduled, and controlled. A key challenge in this space lies in the design of robust strategies that not only optimize long-term production plans but also react effectively to dynamic events and uncertainty on the shop floor.

This challenge is traditionally framed through two interrelated decision-making layers: **scheduling** and **dispatching**. Scheduling refers to the global assignment of operations to machines over time, typically done in advance and optimized for performance metrics such as makespan, tardiness, or resource utilization. Dispatching, by contrast, is the real-time selection of which job to run next when a resource becomes available. It typically operates under local, incomplete information and must respond to unforeseen disruptions such as machine breakdowns or urgent job insertions. [27]

A foundational abstraction for these problems is the Job Shop Scheduling Problem (JSSP), in which each job consists of a fixed sequence of operations that must be processed on specific machines. The classic JSSP assumes single-machine occupancy, rigid routing, and deterministic timing—all of which simplify computation but fall short in describing the behavior of real-world systems. In practice, production lines exhibit greater flexibility, including parallel resource options, hierarchical product structures, batch-based processing, and dynamic job arrivals.

Problem Statement and Motivation

This thesis investigates a specific class of scheduling problem arising in the production of RFID tags. These systems combine electrical and mechanical processes such as wafer metallization, antenna printing, inlay assembly, lamination, and testing. The manufacturing flow is characterized by both converging and sequential stages, with dependencies not only between operations, but also across unit quantities and setup configurations. Resources may differ in capabilities, setup requirements, and throughput speeds, and many operations must process work orders in fixed-size batches.

Furthermore, customer orders are not all known in advance but arrive over time. This dynamic arrival process limits the effectiveness of global schedule optimization and emphasizes the need for real-time, reactive decision-making. Hence, a simulation-based dispatching framework becomes a more suitable choice than static, centralized planning.

Figure I.1: Illustration of RFID production in the semiconductor industry. Source: HERMOS AG [18].

Research Objective and Scope

The central objective of this thesis is to develop, analyze, and evaluate dispatching strategies for a **dynamic flexible assembly job shop scheduling problem with batch-based execution**. We aim to answer the following research questions:

- RQ1** How well can heuristic dispatching rules handle complex scheduling scenarios involving dynamic job arrivals, unit dependencies, and setup times?
- RQ2** Can rule combinations (e.g., sequential or weighted heuristics) outperform individual dispatching strategies across key performance indicators?
- RQ3** How does a metaheuristic approach (e.g., [SA](#)) compare in terms of solution quality and computational cost?

Methodology

To address these questions, we design a discrete-event simulation environment that models the detailed behavior of job shop execution under various constraints. The framework supports:

- Dispatching rule evaluation under dynamic order arrivals;
- Batch-based resource scheduling and unit-level dependency tracking;
- Configurable key performance indices ([KPIs](#)) (e.g., overdue time, priority violation, setup time);
- Metaheuristic optimization using Simulated Annealing for comparison.

Real production data from an RFID manufacturer is used to validate the problem structure and simulation framework. Two synthetic datasets are further constructed to test generalizability and explore a wider range of job and resource configurations.

Contributions

The main contributions of this work are:

- A formal problem definition for the Dynamic Flexible Assembly Job Shop Scheduling Problem with Batch-based Execution;
- A modular simulation-based framework for evaluating dispatching strategies in realistic production environments;
- A comprehensive empirical study of individual, sequential, and weighted dispatching rule combinations;
- A critical comparison of heuristic and metaheuristic methods in terms of runtime, robustness, and KPI performance.

Thesis Structure

The remainder of this thesis is organized as follows:

- Chapter [II](#) reviews related works;
- Chapter [III](#) provides essential background on Bill of Materials([BOM](#)), job shop scheduling, dispatching rules, metaheuristic techniques, and other related concepts used in this thesis;
- Chapter [IV](#) introduces the formal problem definition and modeling framework;
- Chapter [V](#) describes the dispatching rules and optimization strategies used;
- Chapter [VI](#) presents experimental results and analysis;
- Chapter [VII](#) concludes the thesis with a discussion of findings and future directions.

Chapter II Related Works

The JSSP is a classical area of research within operations research and industrial engineering, recognized as an NP-hard problem [11]. The standard JSSP involves scheduling a set of jobs, each with predefined sequences of operations, across a limited set of machines to optimize performance metrics such as makespan, tardiness, or resource utilization. However, practical manufacturing environments frequently introduce additional complexities, such as dynamic job arrivals, flexible machine assignments, preemptions, and assembly constraints. These advanced variations, such as Flexible JSSP and Assembly JSSP, have thus become important subjects of contemporary scheduling research [26, 25, 10].

Dispatching Rules

Dispatching Rules (DRs) are heuristic strategies employed for making rapid, real-time operational decisions concerning which task should be assigned next to an available resource. Common DRs include FIFO, Shortest Processing Time (SPT), Earliest Due Date (EDD), and rules designed to minimize setup time [33, 20, 30]. The primary advantage of DRs lies in their computational efficiency and simplicity, which allows manufacturers to quickly adapt scheduling decisions to real-time changes, such as job arrivals or machine failures [30, 16]. DRs are especially effective in dynamic and complex scenarios where responsiveness is prioritized over global optimality [25].

Extensive research indicates that DRs demonstrate robust performance even when problem complexity increases, such as transitioning from standard JSSP to Flexible or Assembly JSSP. Studies confirm that rules like EDD and SPT remain effective in handling complexities introduced by flexible machine assignments and assembly-level constraints [20, 30]. However, despite their responsiveness and practicality, DRs alone may yield locally optimal solutions, thus motivating the exploration of methods that integrate dispatching heuristics with higher-level optimization techniques.

Metaheuristics

Metaheuristic optimization methods, such as Genetic Algorithms, SA, Tabu Search, and Particle Swarm Optimization, have been extensively studied to solve complex scheduling problems due to their capability of navigating large and intricate solution spaces [26, 22]. In the context of Flexible JSSP, metaheuristics successfully manage complexities arising from multiple machine assignments and operation sequencing decisions [26].

For dynamic scheduling contexts, metaheuristics are commonly embedded into adaptive frameworks, which periodically re-optimize schedules in response to disruptive events, such as new job arrivals or machine breakdowns [25]. Additionally, preemptive scheduling, which allows operation interruptions

and resumptions, has been addressed through specialized metaheuristic approaches, highlighting their adaptability in more intricate manufacturing settings [10].

While metaheuristics offer significant potential in achieving globally competitive scheduling solutions, they require more computational resources and solution times compared to dispatching heuristics[31]. Therefore, their use is often restricted to evaluation or periodic schedule optimization rather than continuous real-time dispatching [25].

Answer Set Programming (ASP)

Answer Set Programming (ASP) is a declarative programming paradigm rooted in logic programming and non-monotonic reasoning [14], well-suited for representing and solving combinatorial problems such as scheduling. In ASP, scheduling constraints are encoded as logic rules, and specialized solvers (e.g., Clingo [13]) are used to compute answer sets that represent feasible schedules.

Recent research has demonstrated the efficacy of ASP in modeling complex shop-floor scenarios, including job shop and flexible job shop problems with resource conflicts, precedence constraints, and domain-specific rules [12, 8]. ASP's expressiveness allows for a natural representation of intricate constraints, such as sequencing, availability, and dynamic changes in production environments.

Although ASP solvers can achieve high-quality solutions, they often incur higher computational costs than dispatching rules and are less scalable in real-time applications. Therefore, ASP is typically used for offline schedule generation, planning, or hybrid integration with simulation and optimization frameworks [4, 21]. Its integration in dynamic contexts, such as semiconductor or RFID manufacturing, remains an emerging research area with promising potential for representing fine-grained control policies and constraint-rich processes.

Matheuristics

Matheuristics combine mathematical programming techniques, such as Mixed Integer Linear Programming, with heuristic procedures, aiming to leverage the strengths of both exact and heuristic methods [5]. In scheduling, matheuristics typically involve solving simplified or decomposed mathematical models, which guide heuristic-based exploration or local search methods to achieve near-optimal solutions efficiently. These hybrid approaches have shown notable success in handling complex scheduling variants such as the Flexible JSSP and Assembly JSSP, providing effective trade-offs between computational time and solution quality [1, 24, 16].

Hybrid Methods

Hybrid methods integrate DRs with advanced optimization techniques such as metaheuristics to improve scheduling performance beyond what either method can achieve individually. Recent research highlights the effectiveness of hybrid genetic algorithms for solving complex scheduling problems, demonstrating significant improvements in objectives such as makespan, tardiness, and machine utilization [19, 7]. These hybrid approaches allow leveraging the responsiveness of DRs while systematically exploring solutions for improved global performance.

RFID and Semiconductor Manufacturing Context

Scheduling in RFID and semiconductor manufacturing presents unique challenges due to complex production flows, high precision requirements, and dynamic operational environments. Operational planning and control research in semiconductor wafer production has emphasized strategies that manage frequent changes in production priorities, complex dependencies among operations, and strict delivery deadlines [17]. Despite extensive literature addressing semiconductor manufacturing scheduling, specific studies integrating real-time dispatching strategies with dynamic simulation and optimization in RFID contexts remain comparatively limited, offering opportunities for new contributions.

Research Gap and Positioning

Given these complexities, this thesis specifically addresses scheduling and dispatching strategies within dynamic, component-based manufacturing environments, exemplified by RFID product manufacturing. While substantial literature exists on each discussed scheduling variation individually, integrative approaches that combine DRs with systematic metaheuristic evaluations in realistic dynamic scenarios are still scarce. This thesis aims to fill this gap by presenting a comprehensive simulation framework for dynamic, assembly-based job shop environments, critically evaluating DRs through benchmarking against metaheuristic-generated solutions, and offering insights broadly applicable to advanced manufacturing contexts beyond RFID production.

Chapter III Fundamentals

This chapter introduces the fundamental concepts and formal definitions that form the theoretical backbone of this thesis. It begins with an overview of BOM and how they can be modeled using tree, to reflect the complex product assembly hierarchies. The chapter then transitions into formal exploration of JSSP and its key variants, including flexible, dynamic, and assembly-based extensions. Finally, it presents dispatching rules and the Simulated Annealing metaheuristic, which serve as important algorithmic foundations for the solution methods developed in this work.

1 Bill of Materials Splitting

1.1 Bill of Materials

A BOM is a comprehensive hierarchical document that lists all the components, subassemblies, raw materials, and intermediate assemblies required to manufacture a product. It serves as a blueprint for product design, procurement, inventory management, and production scheduling.

BOM Splitting is the process of dividing a product's BOM into distinct parts, phases, or categories to manage production more efficiently. This division ensures better tracking, resource allocation, and streamlining of manufacturing processes.

There are several common methods of BOM Splitting, some of them can be listed as following:

- **By Production Phases:** Dividing the BOM by different stages of manufacturing, where each phase focuses on specific components;
- **By Subassemblies:** Breaking the BOM into smaller BOMs for each subassembly (e.g., an electronic device divided into smaller electronic parts);
- **By Supplier and Procurement:** Splitting the BOM based on where components are sourced from, allowing better supplier management.
- **By Functional Grouping:** Grouping components by their function in the product (e.g., electrical parts, mechanical parts);
- **By Material Types:** Categorizing components by the materials they are made from;
- **By Product Variants:** Creating BOM divisions for different product configurations or variants.

In the context of this thesis, we focus on the method of splitting **by Production Phases**. Such BOM is called manufacturing BOM.

While traditional manufacturing BOMs are often represented as tabular structures or tree diagrams, complex assemblies with reusable components and interdependencies benefit from being modeled using a tree.

1.2 Tree structure in manufacturing BOM

1.2.1 Tree structure

A *tree* is a hierarchical structure composed of nodes and edges. Formally, a tree is a graph $T = (V, E)$, where:

- $V = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$ is a finite set of nodes,
- $E \subseteq \{\{u, v\} \mid u, v \in V, u \neq v\}$ is a set of undirected edges,
- The graph is connected, and there are no cycles.

A tree has the following properties:

- There is exactly one *path* between any two nodes.
- A *root node* is a designated starting point of the hierarchy.
- A *leaf node* is a node with no children.
- An *intermediate node* is a node that has both a parent and at least one child.

Unless stated otherwise, all trees in this thesis are assumed to be rooted and finite.

1.2.2 Manufacturing BOM as a Tree

A manufacturing BOM (Bill of Materials) can be naturally represented as a tree, where the hierarchical structure captures the composition of products from components and subassemblies. In this tree:

- each node represents a distinct manufacturing step or part;
- edges indicate that one node (a part or manufacturing step) is required for the construction or processing of another;
- leaf nodes correspond to the initial materials or externally procured components;
- intermediate nodes denote subassemblies that are inputs to higher-level assemblies;
- the root node represents the final product that results from combining all subordinate elements.

The tree structure of a BOM provides a clear and intuitive view of how a product is composed of various layers of parts and operations. This is illustrated in Figure III.1, which depicts a simplified example. The process begins with two raw materials: **Lead Frame** and **Chip**. Each **Lead Frame** undergoes **Metallization** and is then sent to a **Plating**. Concurrently, the **Chip** passes through a **Printing** step. The outputs from Plating and Printing are then joined during the **Assembly** phase. Afterward, the product undergoes **Sheet Cutting**, followed by **Lamination**, and concludes with **Testing**. Items that reach the root of the tree, having passed all required steps, are considered

Figure III.1: Example Manufacturing Bill of Materials

completed products. The direction from leaf nodes to the root thus represents the forward flow of production within the BOM, moving from raw materials to finished goods.

In practical manufacturing environments, there are typically multiple types of products being produced simultaneously, each governed by its own BOM. As a result, the production system comprises multiple trees — one for each final product - that may overlap through the reuse of common steps. These overlapping structures form a broader graph in which components may appear in multiple trees but are assembled independently toward distinct final outputs.

2 Job Shop Scheduling Problem and variants

2.1 Schedule

A **schedule** is a plan that specifies when and where each operation of a production system is executed. In the context of manufacturing and job shop scheduling, it defines the temporal assignment of operations to machines, subject to precedence and resource constraints.

Definition 1 (Schedule) *Given a set of operations \mathcal{O} (i.e., discrete tasks or processing steps to be executed on machines), a set of machines \mathcal{M} , and a set of precedence relations $\prec \subseteq \mathcal{O} \times \mathcal{O}$, a schedule \mathcal{S} is a mapping that assigns:*

- a **start time** $s_o \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ to each operation $o \in \mathcal{O}$,
- a **machine** $m_o \in \mathcal{M}$ capable of processing o ,

such that:

1. **Precedence constraints** are satisfied: $s_{o'} \geq s_o + p_o$ for every $(o, o') \in \prec$, where p_o is the processing time of o .
2. **Resource constraints** hold: no two operations assigned to the same machine overlap in time.
3. **Non-preemption**: once an operation starts, it runs without interruption until completion.

A schedule is considered *feasible* if all these constraints are satisfied. Its *quality* can be evaluated using performance metrics such as makespan, total tardiness, machine utilization, or priority adherence [29, 6, 15].

2.2 Job Shop Scheduling Problem

The Job Shop Scheduling Problem (JSSP) is a classical optimization problem in operations research and production planning, where multiple jobs must be executed across a set of machines. Each job is composed of a strictly ordered sequence of operations, and each operation must be processed on a specific machine for a given duration. A typical example might involve the manufacture of a complex product, such as a car, where each job represents the production of a single unit, and each operation corresponds to a task such as welding, painting, or assembly on a designated machine.

The primary goal of the JSSP is to determine a schedule that assigns operations to machines over time, satisfying technological and resource constraints, while minimizing the overall completion time of all jobs—referred to as the *makespan*.

To enable formal reasoning and algorithmic development, we introduce the following formal definition of the JSSP, consistent with classical treatments in the scheduling literature [27, 6, 15].

Definition 2 (JSSP) Let $J = \{J_1, J_2, \dots, J_n\}$ be the set of jobs and $\mathcal{M} = \{M_1, M_2, \dots, M_m\}$ be the set of machines. Each job J_j consists of a sequence of operations $O_j = \langle O_{j1}, O_{j2}, \dots, O_{jm_j} \rangle$, where each operation O_{jk} must be processed on a machine $\mu(O_{jk}) \in \mathcal{M}$ for a processing time $\Delta_{jk} > 0$. Let s_{jk} and $c_{jk} = s_{jk} + \Delta_{jk}$ denote the start and completion times of operation O_{jk} , and let $C_j = c_{jm_j}$ be the completion time of job J_j .

A feasible schedule must satisfy:

1. **Precedence**: $s_{j,k+1} \geq c_{jk}$;
2. **Machine exclusivity**: If $\mu(O_{jk}) = \mu(O_{j'k'})$, then either $c_{jk} \leq s_{j'k'}$ or $c_{j'k'} \leq s_{jk}$;
3. **Non-preemption**: Once started, operations run to completion.

The objective is to minimize the makespan:

$$C_{\max} = \max_{J_j \in J} C_j$$

The JSSP is well-known to be NP-hard, and solving large instances optimality is computationally challenging due to the combinatorial nature of operation sequencing and machine assignment.

To build intuition, the next section presents a concrete example of the JSSP, highlighting the interplay of job routing, machine conflicts, and timing constraints in a small instance.

Consider a simple instance of the JSSP involving three jobs J_1, J_2, J_3 and three machines M_1, M_2, M_3 . Each job consists of exactly three operations, with each operation assigned to a specific machine and associated with a fixed processing time. The jobs are defined as sequences of ordered pairs (M_i, p) , where M_i denotes the machine and p the required processing time.

Job	Operation Sequence
J_1	$(M_1, 3) \rightarrow (M_2, 2) \rightarrow (M_3, 2)$
J_2	$(M_2, 2) \rightarrow (M_3, 1) \rightarrow (M_1, 4)$
J_3	$(M_3, 4) \rightarrow (M_1, 3) \rightarrow (M_2, 1)$

The objective is to construct a feasible schedule that satisfies the following conditions:

- The operations of each job must be executed in the given order.
- No two operations may overlap on the same machine.
- Optionally, we seek to minimize the overall makespan, i.e., the time required to complete all jobs.

On feasible solution of this example problem can be illustrated as follow:

2.3 Variants of Job Shop Scheduling Problem

While the classical JSSP provides a foundational model for production scheduling, it often proves too restrictive to accurately capture the complexities of real-world manufacturing systems. In industrial environments, scheduling challenges are rarely encountered in the idealized form of the original problem. Instead, practitioners typically deal with various extensions or modifications—known as JSSP variants—that reflect additional flexibility, uncertainty, or structural constraints.

In the scope of this thesis, we focus on three particularly relevant variants, namely flexible, dynamic, and assembly JSSP

Flexible JSSP

The Flexible JSSP extends the classical JSSP by allowing multiple machines to perform each operation. That is, for every operation, instead of assigning it to a predetermined machine, there is a set of eligible machines that can process it, potentially with different processing times.

The goal remains to schedule all operations in the required order, ensuring that

- each operation is assigned to exactly one eligible machine;
- no two operations overlap on the same machine;
- the overall objective is optimized.

This added routing flexibility makes Flexible JSSP significantly more complex but also more realistic for many manufacturing systems, including semiconductor fabs, Computer Numerical Control workshops, and electronics assembly.[9]

Dynamic JSSP

The Dynamic JSSP is an extension of the classical JSSP where not all information is available upfront. In particular:

- jobs may arrive over time, rather than being known at the beginning;
- machine status, such as breakdowns or delays, can change during execution;
- scheduling decisions are made in real-time or incrementally, based on the current system state.

Unlike the static JSSP, where the entire problem is defined in advance, the Dynamic JSSP involves reactive or online scheduling, often with dispatching rules, event-driven logic, or rolling horizon planning. The main challenge is to continuously assign operations to machines in a way that balances objectives like makespan, lateness, or throughput, despite the uncertainty and evolving state of the system.[29]

Assembly JSSP

The Assembly JSSP is an extension of the classical JSSP where jobs are composed of multiple interdependent steps that reflect an assembly structure [28]. Unlike the standard JSSP where each job is a linear sequence of operations, in Assembly JSSP, we have the following characteristics:

- each job consists of a hierarchical graph of steps (a tree);
- some steps (called assembly steps) depend on the completion of other component steps;
- each step must be assigned to an appropriate machine and scheduled such that all precedence and resource constraints are respected.

2.4 Dispatching Rules in JSSP

DRs, also referred to as *scheduling policies* or *priority rules*, are heuristic decision mechanisms used to select the next job to process from a queue of waiting jobs when a resource becomes available. These rules are central to operational control in manufacturing systems, particularly under dynamic and stochastic conditions where real-time decisions must be made and optimal scheduling is computationally infeasible. As defined by Pinedo [29] and elaborated by Morton and Pentico [23], a dispatching rule assigns a priority index to each candidate job, typically based on attributes such as processing time, due date, arrival time, or job class. The job with the highest priority is selected for execution.

Formally, a DR can be defined as a function:

$$R : A(t) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$$

that assigns a numerical priority to each operation $O \in A(t)$, where $A(t)$ is the set of operations available at time t . The next operation selected for processing is

$$O^* = \arg \min_{O \in A(t)} R(O) \quad \text{or} \quad O^* = \arg \max_{O \in A(t)} R(O)$$

depending on the rule's orientation (minimizing or maximizing). The rule operates locally and greedily, without considering future consequences or global optimality.

Commonly applied dispatching rules include SPT, EDD, and FIFO, each targets different performance objectives such as flow time, tardiness, or lateness [3, 2]. In case of priority ties, secondary criteria or tie-breaking heuristics may be used. Unless otherwise specified, dispatching rules assume non-preemptive processing: once an operation starts execution on a resource, it proceeds without interruption until completion.

Illustrative Example

Consider a simple Job Shop instance with two jobs and two machines. The routing and processing times for each job are given below:

Table III.1: Job operation sequences and processing times

Job	Operation Sequence	Processing Times (Machine)
J_1	$O_{11} \rightarrow O_{12}$	$O_{11} : 3$ (on M_1), $O_{12} : 4$ (on M_2)
J_2	$O_{21} \rightarrow O_{22}$	$O_{21} : 2$ (on M_1), $O_{22} : 5$ (on M_2)

At time $t = 0$, both operations O_{11} and O_{21} are ready to be scheduled, and both require machine M_1 . We now apply the SPT dispatching rule, which selects the operation with the shortest duration on the contested machine.

- $R(O_{11}) = 3$
- $R(O_{21}) = 2$

Since $R(O_{21}) < R(O_{11})$, the SPT rule selects O_{21} to be processed first on machine M_1 .

As a result, the initial scheduling decision based on the SPT rule is:

Schedule O_{21} on M_1 from $t = 0$ to $t = 2$

Then schedule O_{11} on M_1 from $t = 2$ to $t = 5$

This example illustrates how dispatching rules can be applied in a step-by-step scheduling process to resolve resource contention.

DRs are particularly valuable in job shop and flexible manufacturing systems due to their simplicity,

adaptability, and low computational cost. They provide a practical framework for near-real-time scheduling, especially when integrated into simulation-based or rule-based control architectures.

3 Simulated Annealing (SA)

SA is a metaheuristic optimization technique inspired by the physical process of annealing in metallurgy, where a material is heated to a high temperature and then slowly cooled to reduce defects and reach a state of minimal energy. This metaphor is transferred to combinatorial optimization problems to explore complex, multimodal search spaces and avoid getting trapped in local optima. Formally, SA can be defined as following:

Definition 3 (Simulated Annealing) *Let S denote the solution space, $f : S \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ the objective function to minimize, and $\mathcal{N}(s) \subseteq S$ the neighborhood function. The algorithm proceeds as follows:*

```
1: Input: Objective function  $f$ , neighborhood function  $\mathcal{N}$ , initial solution  $s_0 \in S$ , initial temperature  $T_0 > 0$ , cooling rate  $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ , maximum iterations  $N_{\max}$ , termination criterion function  $\text{terminate}(\cdot)$ 
2:  $s \leftarrow s_0$ 
3:  $T \leftarrow T_0$ 
4: for  $i = 1$  to  $N_{\max}$  do
5:   if  $\text{terminate}(s, T, i)$  then
6:     break
7:   end if
8:   Select  $s' \in \mathcal{N}(s)$  uniformly at random
9:    $\Delta f \leftarrow f(s') - f(s)$ 
10:  if  $\Delta f \leq 0$  then
11:     $s \leftarrow s'$ 
12:  else
13:    Accept  $s'$  with probability  $\exp(-\Delta f/T)$ 
14:  end if
15:   $T \leftarrow \alpha \cdot T$ 
16: end for
17: return  $s$ 
```

SA distinguishes itself by occasionally accepting worse solutions in order to escape local optima. The likelihood of accepting such solutions depends on the temperature parameter T , which decreases over time. Initially, the algorithm favors exploration by allowing a higher acceptance rate of inferior solutions. As the temperature declines, it shifts toward exploitation, focusing on improvements. The procedure terminates when the temperature falls below a predefined threshold, the solution shows no significant change, or the maximum number of iterations is reached.

Chapter IV Dynamic Flexible Assembly Job Shop Scheduling Problem with Batch-based Execution

We consider a dynamic scheduling problem motivated by real-world manufacturing environments, where customer orders arrive over time and products are produced through multi-stage, component-based processes.

1 Definition

Definition 4 (Dynamic Flexible Assembly Job Shop Scheduling Problem with Batch-Based Execution) *We consider a dynamic job shop scheduling problem with flexible machine assignments, batch-based execution, and hierarchical product structures. Jobs (customer orders) arrive over time and must be scheduled online using a fixed set of predefined steps and machine capabilities.*

Let \mathbb{T} denote the time axis (e.g., timestamps), and let \mathbb{D} denote non-negative durations. To simplify, we denote the unit of duration as hour.

Steps and Product Structure (Globally Known). *In this formulation, steps are synonymous with operations as used in classical job shop scheduling literature. Let $\mathcal{O} = \{O_1, O_2, \dots, O_n\}$ be the set of steps defined in the manufacturing system. Each step $O_i \in \mathcal{O}$ is characterized by:*

- A processing mode assignment given by a partition of \mathcal{O} into:

$$\mathcal{O}_M \subseteq \mathcal{O} \quad (\text{machine-required steps}), \quad \mathcal{O}_N \subseteq \mathcal{O} \quad (\text{non-machine steps})$$

such that:

$$\mathcal{O}_M \cap \mathcal{O}_N = \emptyset, \quad \mathcal{O}_M \cup \mathcal{O}_N = \mathcal{O}$$

- For $O_i \in \mathcal{O}_M$, a fixed work order size $l_i \in \mathbb{N}$, denotes the number of units produced per work order.
- For $O_i \in \mathcal{O}_N$, a fixed make time $\Delta_i \in \mathbb{D}$, representing the duration needed to process all required units once the step becomes eligible.
- A set of immediate predecessor steps $\text{pred}(O_i) \subseteq \mathcal{O}$; the induced subgraph of O_i and its transitive predecessors forms a directed tree rooted at O_i . O_i is called successor of every element in $\text{pred}(O_i)$.
- For each machine-required step $O_i \in \mathcal{O}_M$, a set of eligible machines $\mathcal{M}_i \subseteq \mathcal{M}$, and for each

machine $M_h \in \mathcal{M}_i$:

- processing speed $u_{ih} \in \mathbb{R}^+$ (units/hour), denoting how many units machine M_h can process per hour for step O_i ;
- success ratio $\sigma_{ih} \in (0, 1]$, a factor that inflates the processing time of a work order, in which a success ratio less than 1 means that more time is required to complete the same number of units, due to imperfect yields or retries;
- setup time $\delta_{ih} \in \mathbb{D}$ when switching from a different step (if not given, it is by default $\delta_{ih} = 0$).
- For each edge (O_p, O_i) , where $O_p \in \text{pred}(O_i)$, a transition delay $\tau_{pi} \in \mathbb{D}$ must elapse after O_p completes before O_i may begin.

This entire step network, including all precedence constraints, work order sizes, and machine configurations, is known at the start of the scheduling horizon.

Customer Orders (Dynamically Revealed). In this formulation, customer orders are synonymous with jobs as used in classical job shop scheduling literature. We denote the set of jobs (customer orders) by $\mathcal{J} = \langle J_1, J_2, \dots \rangle$, where each job $J_j \in \mathcal{J}$ becomes visible at its release time $r_j \in \mathbb{T}$ and is defined by:

- release time $r_j \in \mathbb{T}$;
- due time $d_j \in \mathbb{T}$ with $d_j > r_j$;
- required quantity $q_j \in \mathbb{N}$;
- a priority level $\pi_j \in \{\text{VERY LOW} < \text{LOW} < \text{NORMAL} < \text{HIGH} < \text{CRITICAL}\}$, indicating the urgency or importance of the job;
- a designated final step $O_j^{\text{final}} \in \mathcal{O}$, identifying the final product type.

Upon arrival at time r_j , a job-specific step subgraph $G_j = (\mathcal{O}_j, E_j)$ is instantiated, derived from the tree rooted at O_j^{final} , including all dependencies.

In the problem, a job's demand for a particular step must be fulfilled through the execution of one or more *work orders*. A work order represents a concrete, schedulable batch of units to be processed for a specific step.

Work Orders and Execution. Each step $O_i \in \mathcal{O}_j$ for job J_j must produce q_j units.

If $O_i \in \mathcal{O}_M$, these units are fulfilled by creating a sequence of work orders $\langle W_{ij1}, \dots, W_{ijz} \rangle$, each processing at most l_i units, in which l_i is the fixed work order size of step O_i predefined above. Each work order W_{ijk} for $0 < k \leq z$ (in which k is the index of work order in sequence of step O_i) is defined by:

$$W_{ijk} = (s_{ijk}, c_{ijk}, M_{ijk}, q_{ijk})$$

where:

- $s_{ijk}, c_{ijk} \in \mathbb{T}$ are the start and completion times,

- $M_{ijk} \in \mathcal{M}_i$ is the assigned machine (for $O_i \in \mathcal{O}_M$),
- $q_{ijk} \leq l_i$ is the quantity produced in the work order.

By default, q_{ijk} is set to the full work order size l_i to maximize batching efficiency and machine utilization. The only exception occurs when fewer than l_i units remain to be scheduled—typically in the last work order—where the quantity q_{ijk} is set to the residual demand for step O_i within job J_j , i.e., the remaining $q_j \bmod l_i$ units.

Work orders are **non-preemptive** and must run to completion once started.

The processing duration of a work order W_{ijk} , denoted $\Delta_{ijk} \in \mathbb{D}$, depends on the fixed batch size l_i , the assigned machine M_{ijk} , and whether a setup is required. For readability, let $M_{ijk} = M_h \in \mathcal{M}_i$ denote the machine assigned to work order W_{ijk} , and use the corresponding machine index h to refer to parameters u_{ih} , σ_{ih} , and δ_{ih} (units per hour (UPH), success ratio, and setup time respectively). The actual quantity q_{ijk} does not influence the processing time. Specifically:

$$\Delta_{ijk} = \begin{cases} \frac{l_i}{\sigma_{ih} \cdot u_{ih}} + \delta_{ih} & \text{if setup is required,} \\ \frac{q_{ijk}}{\sigma_{ih} \cdot u_{ih}} & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

and the completion time is:

$$c_{ijk} = s_{ijk} + \Delta_{ijk}.$$

Non-Machine Step. For each non-machine step $O_i \in \mathcal{O}_N$ required by job J_j , the execution is modeled as a single, non-preemptive block without batching or machine assignment. This execution is represented by the tuple:

$$(s_{ij}, c_{ij}) \in \mathbb{T} \times \mathbb{T}$$

where s_{ij} is the start time and $c_{ij} = s_{ij} + \Delta_i$ is the completion time, given a fixed make time $\Delta_i \in \mathbb{D}$. Execution begins as soon as all predecessor steps have provided the required total quantity q_j , and any transition delays τ_{pi} have elapsed.

Unit Availability and Propagation. For each job J_j and step $O_i \in \mathcal{O}$, we define the function $available_j^i(t) \in \mathbb{N}$ as the number of units produced by O_i that are still available for successor step consumption at time $t \in \mathbb{T}$.

This function changes over time as follows:

- **Increment (production):** When a machine-based work order W_{ijk} for step $O_i \in \mathcal{O}_M$ completes at time c_{ijk} , the quantity q_{ijk} is added to $available_j^i(t)$ starting at time c_{ijk} .

For non-machine steps $O_i \in \mathcal{O}_N$, the entire quantity q_j becomes available at time c_{ij} , and q_j is added to $available_j^i(t)$ at $t = c_{ij}$.

- **Decrement (consumption):** When a successor step O_k with $O_i \in \text{pred}(O_k)$ begins producing a work order that requires q units from O_i , then $available_j^i(t)$ is updated by $-q$ at the start time of that work order (or non-machine step).

The function is formally expressed as:

$$available_j^i(t) = \begin{cases} \underbrace{\sum_{W_{ijk}; c_{ijk} \leq t} q_{ijk}}_{\text{produced (machine)}} - \underbrace{\sum_{W_{hjk}; s_{hjk} \leq t} q_{hjk}}_{\text{consumed by successor}} & \text{if } O_i \in \mathcal{O}_M, \\ \underbrace{\mathbf{1}_{\{c_{ij} \leq t\}} \cdot q_j}_{\text{produced (non-machine)}} - \underbrace{\sum_{W_{hjk}; s_{hjk} \leq t} q_{hjk}}_{\text{consumed by successor}} & \text{if } O_i \in \mathcal{O}_N \end{cases}$$

where O_{j_h} is successor of O_i in J_j .

If multiple events are scheduled at the same timestamp t , they are applied in the following order:

1. All production events at time t are applied first (in any order);
2. All consumption events at time t are applied afterwards.

Feasibility Constraints. A schedule is feasible if the following conditions hold:

1. **Information visibility:** Job J_j and all associated demands are unknown until $t = r_j$.
2. **Precedence and transitions:**

A work order W_{ijk} can only start after enough units from all predecessors are available, and transition times are respected:

$$s_{ijk} \geq \max_{O_p \in \text{pred}(O_i)} \left\{ \min \left\{ t \in \mathbb{T} \mid available_j^p(t) \geq q_{ijk} \right\} + \tau_{pi} \right\}$$

That is, it must wait until the latest among the earliest times at which each predecessor has produced enough units—plus its required transition delay—has passed.

Under normal circumstances, $q_{ijk} = l_i$ for all work orders except the final one.

For each step $O_i \in \mathcal{O}_N$ required by job J_j , the start time s_{ij} must satisfy:

$$s_{ij} \geq \max_{O_p \in \text{pred}(O_i)} \left\{ \min \left\{ t \in \mathbb{T} \mid available_j^p(t) \geq q_i \right\} + \tau_{pi} \right\}$$

3. **Machine capacity:** No two work orders may be processed concurrently on the same machine. That is, for any two work orders

$$W_{ijk} = (s_{ijk}, c_{ijk}, M_h, q_{ijk}) \quad \text{and} \quad W_{uvw} = (s_{uvw}, c_{uvw}, M_h, q_{uvw})$$

assigned to the same machine M_h and their execution intervals must not overlap. Without loss of generality, assume $s_{ijk} \geq s_{uvw}$; then it must hold that:

$$s_{ijk} \geq c_{uvw}$$

4. **Setup condition:** The processing duration Δ_{ijk} of a work order already incorporates a setup time δ_{ih} if required. A setup is needed whenever the preceding work order on the same machine

 Figure IV.1: Step dependency of O_1

processed a different step. Specifically, let $\mathcal{W}_h = \{W_{ijk} \in \mathcal{W} \mid M_{ijk} = M_h\}$ denote the set of all work orders assigned to machine M_h , ordered by their start time s_{ijk} . Let W_{ijk}^{prev} denote the most recent work order on machine M_h that finishes before s_{ijk} . Then, if W_{ijk}^{prev} exists and its step differs from O_i , a setup is required:

$$\text{if } O_{prev} \neq O_i \quad \Rightarrow \quad \Delta_{ijk} = \frac{l_i}{\sigma_{ih} \cdot u_{ih}} + \delta_{ih}$$

Otherwise, if the step is the same:

$$\Delta_{ijk} = \frac{l_i}{\sigma_{ih} \cdot u_{ih}}$$

Completion Time and Objective. The completion time C_j of job J_j is defined as the latest completion of all work orders of its final step O_j^{final} . The goal is to minimize a scheduling performance criterion, such as:

$$\min \sum_{J_j \in \mathcal{J}} \max(0, C_j - d_j) \quad (\text{total overdue time}) \quad \text{or} \quad \min \max_j C_j \quad (\text{makespan})$$

2 Illustrative Example

To better illustrate the problem, we present a detailed example to demonstrate the core constraints of the original problem. Consider a single customer order J_1 released at time $t = 0$ (January 1st, 00:00), which requires $q_1 = 25$ units of a final product step O_1 , and has due date at time $t = 36$ hours (January 2nd, 12:00). The product has a hierarchical structure: each unit of O_1 must be assembled from one unit of O_2 and one unit of O_3 , where O_2 and O_3 are independent steps (i.e., $\text{pred}(O_1) = \{O_2, O_3\}$). The production tree for step O_1 is shown in Figure IV.1

Work Order Sizes and Transitions. Each step is executed in fixed-size work orders, defined as follows:

The work order size defines the maximum number of units that can be processed in a single execution. When the remaining quantity is smaller than this capacity, the system allows the creation of a *partial work order* to produce exactly the required number of units without overproduction. To ensure consistency, such partial work orders are generated only once per step and customer order—specifically

O_i	l_i	τ_{i1} (h)
O_2	6	5
O_3	4	6
O_1	7	-

Table IV.1: Step-specific work order sizes and transition delays

to fulfill the residual demand.

In this scenario, to meet the target of 25 units, the following number of work orders are required:

- $\lceil \frac{25}{6} \rceil = 5$ for O_2 ,
- $\lceil \frac{25}{4} \rceil = 7$ for O_3 ,
- $\lceil \frac{25}{7} \rceil = 4$ for O_1 .

Machine Capabilities. Each step is eligible on a specific machine:

M_h	O_i	u_{ih}	σ_{ih}	δ_{ih}
M_1	O_1	7	0.33	1
M_2	O_2	2	0.75	1
M_3	O_3	1	1.00	0

Table IV.2: Machine-step performance parameters

For each work order W_{ijk} processing time is computed as:

$$\Delta_{ijk} = \frac{l_i}{\sigma_{ih} \cdot u_{ih}} + \delta_{ih}(\text{if any})$$

where M_h is the machine chosen to process W_{ijk} . Hence, processing time for each work order is calculated as follows:

- O_1 : $\frac{7}{7 \cdot 0.33} \approx 3$ hours (+1 hour setup if switching),
- O_2 : $\frac{6}{2 \cdot 0.75} = 4$ hours (+1 hour setup),
- O_3 : $\frac{4}{1 \cdot 1.0} = 4$ hours (no setup).

Execution Timeline and Unit Accumulation. At $t = 0$, no units of O_2 or O_3 are yet available, so no work order of O_1 can be started. However, machines M_2 and M_3 can begin their respective first work orders:

- W_{311} finishes at $t = 4$ (no setup), meaning $c_{311} = 4$;
- W_{211} finishes at $t = 5$ (including 1-hour setup), meaning $c_{211} = 5$.

At this point, available units:

$$available_2^1(t = 5) = 6, \quad available_3^1(t = 4) = 4$$

However, to initiate a work order $W_{O_1,1}$, we need:

$$\min(available_2^1(t), available_3^1(t)) \geq 7$$

which is not yet satisfied at $t = 5$, so O_1 remains blocked.

Production continues:

- $c_{32} = 8$,
- $c_{22} = 9$,

Now the cumulative units are:

$$available_2^1(t = 9) = 6 + 6 = 12, \quad available_3^1(t = 8) = 4 + 4 = 8$$

It is now feasible to start W_{111} . However, due to transition times:

$$s_{111} \geq \max(9 + 5, 8 + 6) = 14$$

Suppose W_{111} starts at $t = 14$, consuming 7 units from both O_2 and O_3 , meaning $s_{111} = 14$. Remaining stock:

$$available_2^1(t = 14) = 12 - 7 = 5, \quad available_3^1(t = 14) = 8 - 7 = 1$$

The system continues similarly: new work orders of O_2 and O_3 replenish units, and work orders of O_1 are started only when both predecessor units reach at least 7, after satisfying their respective transition delays.

Final Work Order Flexibility. The final work order $W_{O_1,4}$ is allowed to use fewer than 7 units from each component, as long as the total output reaches the exact required 25 units. Any overproduced units beyond this are discarded and not reusable for other orders.

The complete illustration of the dynamic production process described above is provided in Figure IV.2.

Dynamic Arrival and Resource Contention. Suppose there are multiple customer orders in the system. At time $t = 12$ hours (January 1st, 12:00), a second customer order J_2 is released. This order requires $q_2 = 20$ units of a final product step O_4 , with a due date at $t = 30$ hours. Unlike O_1 , step O_4 has no dependencies:

$$\text{pred}(O_4) = \emptyset$$

Figure IV.2: Example schedule

Machine Allocation for O_4 . Step O_4 shares a machine with O_2 , specifically M_2 . The machine-step configurations are as follows:

M_h	O_i	u_{ih}	σ_{ih}	δ_{ih}
M_2	O_2	2	0.75	1
M_2	O_4	5	0.90	1

 Table IV.3: Machine M_2 shared by steps O_2 and O_4

Let the lot size for O_4 be $l_4 = 10$ units. To fulfill $q_2 = 20$, the scheduler creates two work orders:

- W_{421} : 10 units,
- W_{422} : 10 units.

The processing time per work order of O_4 using machine M_2 is:

$$\Delta_{42k} = \frac{10}{5 \cdot 0.9} = \frac{10}{4.5} \approx 2.22 \text{ hours} + \delta_{42} \text{ (if applicable)}$$

where k is the index of the work order

Online Visibility and Scheduling Decision. Before time $t = 12$, no information about order J_2 is available to the scheduling system. Only at its release time does the system learn the quantity, due date, and required step O_4 . Since O_4 and O_2 both rely on machine M_2 , a resource contention arises: only one step can be executed at a time, and switching between steps incurs setup time. Here we consider two scenarios as following:

Scenario A: Immediate Start of O_4 . If the scheduler chooses to start processing work orders of O_4 immediately upon release, then any pending or future work orders of O_2 must wait. The sequence unfolds as follows:

1. Machine M_2 finishes an O_2 work order and switches to O_4 , incurring a setup time.
2. Two work orders of O_4 are executed in sequence.

Figure IV.3: Scenario A: Immediate processing of dynamically arriving step O_4 , causing two setup transitions

3. Machine M_2 must set up again to switch back to O_2 .

This results in two setup transitions: $O_2 \rightarrow O_4$, and $O_4 \rightarrow O_2$. A complete illustration of this scenario is shown in Figure IV.3.

Scenario B: Deferred Start of O_4 . Alternatively, if the scheduler delays processing of O_4 until all pending O_2 work orders are completed, the setup overhead can be minimized:

1. Machine M_2 finishes all scheduled work orders of O_2 ,
2. Then switches to O_4 , requiring only a single setup transition,
3. Processes both work orders of O_4 consecutively.

This strategy reduces the number of setups but potentially delays the completion of J_2 , which may be unacceptable depending on its urgency or due date. The corresponding timeline is shown in Figure IV.4.

Scheduling Implication. This example demonstrates a key feature of the dynamic flexible assembly job shop problem: dispatching decisions made at runtime must balance resource contention, setup penalties, and due date adherence in the presence of dynamically arriving orders. Since orders are revealed only at their release time, the scheduler cannot optimize globally and must rely on local or heuristic strategies to react effectively.

Figure IV.4: Scenario B: Deferring O_4 reduces setup frequency but delays order J_2

Chapter V Solution Approaches

In this chapter, we present the scheduling approaches evaluated in the context of the Dynamic Flexible Assembly Job Shop Scheduling Problem introduced earlier. Two complementary classes of strategies are explored: (1) rule-based methods built on dispatching heuristics, and (2) a metaheuristic optimization method based on SA.

The first part of the chapter focuses on DRs - simple yet powerful heuristics that guide real-time decision-making at the level of individual work orders. We introduce a library of quantified DRs, discuss their sequential and weighted combinations, and demonstrate how they can be used to prioritize competing tasks in a dynamic production environment.

In the second part, we describe a metaheuristic approach using SA to search for improved scheduling solutions over a finite time horizon. Unlike DRs, which operate greedily and locally, the SA framework allows for a more thorough exploration of the solution space by probabilistically accepting non-improving moves. This enables it to escape local optima and iteratively refine complete schedules through controlled neighborhood transitions.

1 Dispatching Rule Methods

This section introduces rule-based scheduling strategies that prioritize work orders based on simple, interpretable heuristics. We begin by formalizing DRs as numerical functions and then explore mechanisms for combining them to support multi-criteria decision-making in dynamic environments.

1.1 Problem Simulation

Simulation Tool. We implemented the environment using `Kalasin`¹, a discrete-event simulation framework for programming language `Kotlin`. `Kalasin` provides process-oriented modeling via coroutines, event scheduling, and resource management, making it suitable for replicating dynamic, time-based manufacturing scenarios. Its extensibility and integration with `Kotlin`'s type system allow for precise modeling of asynchronous workflows and state transitions. Readers interested in reproducing or extending the experiments can refer to `Kalasin`'s documentation for further details.

This section builds on the formal model introduced in Definition 4 and focuses on its realization within a discrete-event simulation framework. Unless stated otherwise, core concepts such as the structure of customer orders, product dependencies, and batching rules remain consistent with earlier

¹<https://www.kalasin.org/>

Figure V.1: Simulated Environment

definitions. The following discussion elaborates specifically on the implementation mechanisms within the simulation, complemented by illustrative examples.

We conceptually divide the simulation model into two parallel yet interacting processes, represented by separate diagrams: the environment and the machine, illustrated respectively in Figures V.1 and V.2.

The environment dynamically receives customer orders throughout the simulation horizon, respecting the predefined release times. It systematically handles production dependencies defined by the BOM, ensuring that each production step accurately reflects predecessor requirements. As input units become available from completed production steps, the Environment tracks their availability and creates corresponding work orders. These dynamically generated *unscheduled work orders* are immediately dispatched to the *waiting lists* \mathcal{Q}_h of all $M_h \in \mathcal{M}_i$ that are eligible to execute the associated step O_i . These waiting lists \mathcal{Q}_h represent local queues maintained by each machine M_h .

Work Order Instantiation in Simulation. While Definition 4 treats a work order as a fully specified and schedulable entity—complete with a start time, machine assignment, and completion time—our simulation introduces an intermediate representation called an *unscheduled work order*. This construct reflects a concrete unit of production that has been generated by the environment, but has not yet been assigned to a machine or scheduled for execution.

For each unscheduled work order W_{ijk} , only the quantity q_{ijk} is known at creation time. The start time s_{ijk} must satisfy $s_{ijk} \geq created_{ijk}$, where $created_{ijk}$ is the timestamp at which the work order is generated. The machine assignment M_{ijk} is chosen later from the set of eligible machines \mathcal{M}_i , and the completion time c_{ijk} is determined dynamically upon dispatch and execution.

Figure V.2: Simulated Machine

Figure 3: Interaction Loop between Environment and Machines

Figure V.3: Simulated Machine-Environment connection

Each machine $M_h \in \mathcal{M}$ operates autonomously, maintaining its own local waiting list \mathcal{Q}_h . When M_h becomes idle, it evaluates the work orders $W_{ijk} \in \mathcal{Q}_h$ using a predefined DR. Once selected, the work order is removed from the waiting lists of all other eligible machines to prevent duplicate execution. The machine then processes the work order, incorporating any required setup time and applying processing parameters such as throughput rate and success ratio. Upon completion, the machine updates the global unit availability state, enabling the environment to determine whether dependent steps can now be scheduled. This interaction forms a closed-loop system where machines continuously consume work orders and trigger the generation of new ones based on production progress.

This continuous and mutual interaction between the environment-driven generation of work orders and machine-driven unit production creates a robust feedback loop that accurately captures the complexity and dynamism inherent in real-world manufacturing systems. The comprehensive interaction mechanism connecting these two processes is depicted in Figure V.3, emphasizing their interdependence and iterative exchange of information throughout the simulation. Notably, this diagram also distinguishes between two separate actions: the addition of an unscheduled work order to waiting lists of suitable machines and its subsequent execution by a machine. Unscheduled work orders can be enqueued into waiting lists of eligible machines at any point in time, immediately upon their creations. In contrast, the decision to begin processing work orders is solely made by machines when they become idle, guided by DRs.

Situations may arise in which multiple machines become idle at the same simulation timestamp and are concurrently eligible to execute the same pending work order. Because work orders are initially

Figure V.4: Example Bills of Material

placed into the waiting lists of all machines capable of executing the corresponding production step, a contention scenario emerges wherein multiple machines may simultaneously prioritize the same work order for execution. To avoid this issue, we employ a structured approach in our simulation as follows: whenever two or more machines become available simultaneously, their decisions to select the next work order are executed sequentially in a predefined order (typically aligning with the sequence in which machines are listed in the simulation), even if their waiting lists do not intersect.

It is important to note that, despite this sequential decision-making, the machines do not communicate with each other and remain unaware of each other's processing capabilities or completion times. Although this approach might initially seem suboptimal, in practice, given the high number of machines and work orders, the resulting performance impact is negligible.

Example 1.1. To illustrate the described mechanisms concretely, consider a simulated manufacturing environment starting at 00:00 on January 1st, 2024, which includes two dynamically released customer orders:

- The first order, J_1 , is released immediately at the start of the simulation. It requests 25 units of product O_3 , with a due date of January 2nd, 2024, at 00:00, and is assigned *NORMAL* priority.
- The second order, J_2 , is released at 04:00, requesting 10 units of product O_5 , due by January 2nd, 2024, at 01:00, and assigned *LOW* priority.

These orders initiate production steps following the predefined BOM structure shown in Figure V.4. Product O_3 , requested by order J_1 , depends on completion of its inputs O_1 and O_2 , whereas product O_5 , requested by J_2 , first requires step O_4 , itself dependent on the availability of units from step O_1 . Leaf-level steps O_1 and O_2 , having no predecessor dependencies, commence production immediately upon the release of their corresponding customer order. By contrast, dependent steps such as O_3 , O_4 , and O_5 must wait until all required input units have been produced and transitioned into availability.

Detailed simulation parameters including work order sizes, machine capabilities, and transition times are presented in Tables V.1–V.2–V.3–V.4. For instance, the work order sizes for machine-dependent

steps are defined explicitly (e.g., step O_1 has a work order size of 4 units, and step O_2 has a work order size of 6 units).

Table V.1: Work order sizes of machine-dependent production steps

O_i	l_i
O_1	4
O_2	6
O_3	7
O_5	4

Table V.2: Make time of non-machine steps

O_i	Δ_i
O_4	6h

Table V.3: Transition time between steps

O_p	O_i	τ_{pi} (h)
O_2	O_3	5
O_1	O_3	4
O_1	O_4	3
O_4	O_5	2

Suppose in this simulation, **Due Date** is used, meaning work orders with more urgent due time will be prioritized. The complete explanation of **Due Date** as well as other DRs are shown in the next chapter. At simulation start (00:00), only customer order J_1 is visible, and the environment immediately generates initial work orders. Specifically, for the leaf steps O_1 and O_2 , it dynamically creates multiple work orders to fulfill the total demand based on their respective work order sizes. Step O_1 , needing to produce 25 units, results in 7 work orders (six batches of 4 units and one work order of 1 unit). Step O_2 , also required to produce 25 units, results in 5 work orders (four work orders of 6 units and one work order of 1 unit).

Machines operate autonomously, continuously monitoring their waiting lists and selecting work orders based on predefined DRs. Initially, when the seven work orders for step O_1 are created, they are simultaneously added to the waiting lists of both machines M_3 and M_4 , as both machines have the capability to process step O_1 . At this point, both machines M_3 and M_4 are idle and each independently selects one of the available work orders.

Since all seven work orders share the same due date, **Due Date** rule alone cannot differentiate priority among them. However, because six of these work orders are full work orders and one is partial, and 6 full work orders are identical, machines prioritize processing full work orders first (the choosing process is random between these 6 work orders, as they are treated equally, and there is no difference which work orders are processed first). Machine M_3 processes its selected work order of 4 units in 4 hours, while machine M_4 processes its work order of 4 units in 2 hours, both according to their throughput rates and success ratios. When each machine selects a work order, that particular work order is immediately removed from the waiting lists of both machines, leaving five remaining work orders in each of the machines' waiting lists.

Simultaneously, the five work orders for step O_2 are added to the waiting list of machine M_2 , as this machine has the required capability. Machine M_2 , initially idle, selects one of these available work

Table V.4: Machine capabilities and processing characteristics per step

O_i	M_h	u_{ih}	σ_{ih}	δ_{ih}
O_1	M_3	1	1.0	0
O_1	M_4	2	1.0	0
O_2	M_2	2	0.75	1h
O_3	M_1	7	0.33	0
O_3	M_2	7	0.5	0.5h
O_5	M_1	4	1.0	0
O_5	M_3	1	1.0	0

orders and begins processing. It first undergoes a required 1-hour setup period, followed by processing the work order of 6 units in 3 hours. As soon as machine M_2 selects a work order, it is immediately removed from its waiting list, leaving four work orders remaining in the queue.

At simulation time 04:00, customer order J_2 is visible, and the Environment generates initial work orders. Similar to customer order J_1 , 3 work orders of O_1 are created, in which two of them are full work orders and one is partial work order. They are all added to waiting lists of machine M_3 and M_4 . At 04:00, coincidentally, both machine M_3 and M_4 become available, and they choose the next work orders. However, as work orders of step O_1 for J_2 have later due date in comparison to work orders of step O_1 for J_1 , machines M_3 and M_4 continue choosing work orders of step O_1 for J_1 .

At simulation time 06:00, six work orders of step O_1 associated with order J_1 have already been processed, leaving only one partial work order remaining in the waiting lists of machines M_3 and M_4 . Theoretically, either machine could select this remaining partial work order, risking duplicate processing if both select it simultaneously. In this specific scenario, machine M_3 is predetermined to choose first (because it is listed before M_4 and thus selects the last partial work order for step O_1 of order J_1). Consequently, this work order is immediately removed from the waiting lists of both machines, leaving no remaining O_1 work orders for order J_1 . Following this removal, machine M_4 selects and processes a full work order for step O_1 associated with the second customer order, J_2 .

As machines complete their work orders, the environment continuously monitors and dynamically updates the global availability of units produced. When sufficient units from preceding production steps become available and have undergone their respective transition times, the environment proactively generates new work orders for dependent production steps, adhering closely to incremental unit availability.

For example, at simulation time 02:00, 4 units of step O_1 associated with customer order J_1 become available, and at 04:00, an additional 12 units from step O_1 (for J_1) are available. Similarly, at 05:00, 6 units of step O_2 (for J_1) become available, with another 6 units becoming available by 09:00. Each of these units must undergo a specified transition delay before they are available for subsequent steps: 4 hours for step O_1 and 5 hours for step O_2 . Consequently, at simulation time 14:00, a total of 12 units from each of steps O_1 and O_2 (for order J_1) are available for the production of the successor step, O_3 .

The creation of new work orders strictly adheres to the feasibility constraints outlined in Definition 4. At 14:00, even though more units from step O_1 may have completed their transition time and thus be theoretically available, only 12 units of step O_2 are ready. Therefore, the simulation can create at most

Figure V.5: Schedule using DR Due Date

one work order for step O_3 , since its batch size is $l_3 = 7$. If more than one work order were desired, at least 14 units of both O_1 and O_2 would be required. After creating this single work order, the available units of O_1 and O_2 are reduced by the batch size $l_3 = 7$, leaving the remaining units available for future work orders. It is important to note that although additional units from O_1 associated with order J_1 remain, these units cannot be used for the production of step O_4 , as they are specifically allocated to customer order J_1 and thus cannot be transferred to another order such as J_2 .

The newly created work order for step O_3 is immediately added to the waiting lists of machines M_1 and M_2 , as both machines possess the capability to process it. Because machine M_1 is listed first in the simulation sequence and is currently idle, it selects this newly available work order and begins processing. The simulation then continues following these established procedures.

Non-machine steps like O_4 of customer order J_2 can only begin execution when *all* required units of predecessor steps are available. Specifically, step O_4 must wait until all 10 units of O_1 allocated for J_2 are completed before starting.

Once step O_4 completes its processing and produces the required 10 units, these units become available to step O_5 after an additional transition delay of 2 hours, representing material transfer or inspection.

The process continues until there is no unscheduled work order left. The complete schedule of the simulation is shown in Figure V.5.

1.2 Dispatching Rules

In the proposed simulation framework, each machine autonomously selects its next work order from a local queue based on a predefined DR. These rules determine the priority with which work orders are processed and directly influence the system's responsiveness to due dates, production progress, and efficiency goals.

To comprehensively understand the trade-offs associated with different decision-making strategies,

this work implements and evaluates a diverse set of DRs. Each rule reflects a distinct scheduling philosophy, from due-date orientation to workload balancing. The goal is not to favor one particular heuristic upfront, but to provide a systematic comparison of their strengths and weaknesses under realistic assembly job shop conditions.

The following DRs are implemented and examined individually in the evaluation:

- **Due Date:** Prioritizes work orders from customer orders with the earliest due date. This rule focuses on timely delivery and aims to reduce tardiness.

Given two unscheduled work orders W_{ijk} and W_{mnp} in the waiting list \mathcal{Q}_h of machine M_h , where W_{ijk} belongs to job J_j with due date d_j , and W_{mnp} belongs to job J_n with due date d_n , the rule defines the following preference:

$$d_j < d_n \quad \Rightarrow \quad W_{ijk} \text{ is prioritized over } W_{mnp}.$$

- **Available Date:** Prioritizes work orders whose associated customer orders became available earlier. This encourages early response to older backlog orders.

For work orders W_{ijk} and W_{mnp} , with release times r_j and r_n , the rule applies:

$$r_j < r_n \quad \Rightarrow \quad W_{ijk} \text{ is prioritized over } W_{mnp}.$$

- **FIFO:** Work orders are scheduled in the order they were created. This rule ensures fairness and avoids starvation, but does not consider urgency or efficiency.

For work orders W_{ijk} and W_{mnp} , with creation timestamps $created_{ijk}$ and $created_{mnp}$, the preference is:

$$created_{ijk} < created_{mnp} \quad \Rightarrow \quad W_{ijk} \text{ is prioritized.}$$

- **Random Selection:** Work orders are selected uniformly at random. This serves as a baseline heuristic for performance comparison.
- **Minimize Setup Time:** Prioritizes work orders that require minimal setup effort, favoring continuation of the same step type as the previous job. This improves machine utilization and reduces idle time. If setup is unavoidable (i.e., the next job must involve a step type different from the previous one), it selects the work order with the shortest required setup time among the candidates.

Let O_{prev} denote the step of the last processed work order on machine M_h . For two work orders W_{ijk} and W_{mnp} , with steps O_i and O_m , respectively, the rule defines the following preference:

$$O_i = O_{\text{prev}} \wedge O_m \neq O_{\text{prev}} \quad \Rightarrow \quad W_{ijk} \text{ is prioritized over } W_{mnp}.$$

If both steps differ from the previous one:

$$O_i \neq O_{\text{prev}} \wedge O_m \neq O_{\text{prev}} \wedge \delta_{ih} < \delta_{mh} \quad \Rightarrow \quad W_{ijk} \text{ is prioritized.}$$

- **Less Total Units First:** Gives priority to work orders whose associated production steps require fewer total units to be completed. This supports fast closure of near-finished steps.

Let q_j, q_n be the total units to be produced for customer order J_j, J_n :

$$q_j < q_n \quad \Rightarrow \quad W_{ijk} \text{ is prioritized.}$$

- **More Total Units First:** Prioritizes work orders for steps with a large number of remaining units. This rule is often beneficial in early-stage processing to accelerate throughput.

Opposite of the previous rule:

$$q_j > q_n \quad \Rightarrow \quad W_{ijk} \text{ is prioritized.}$$

- **Lowest Percentage Left:** This rule prioritizes steps that are closest to completion relative to their total required units. In simulation time t , let $u_i(t)$ denote the number of units still to be produced for step O_i . Then, the percentage of units remaining is:

$$\rho_i(t) = \frac{u_i(t)}{p_j}.$$

Given two work orders W_{ijk} and W_{mnp} , with respective steps O_i, O_m , the rule prefers:

$$\rho_i(t) < \rho_m(t) \quad \Rightarrow \quad W_{ijk} \text{ is prioritized.}$$

- **Highest Percentage Left:** This rule does the opposite — it prioritizes steps that still have a large proportion of their required units remaining:

$$\rho_i(t) > \rho_m(t) \quad \Rightarrow \quad W_{ijk} \text{ is prioritized.}$$

- **Higher Priority First:** Let $\pi_j, \pi_n \in \{VERY\ LOW < LOW < NORMAL < HIGH < CRITICAL\}$ denote the priority levels of jobs J_j and J_n , associated with work orders W_{ijk} and W_{mnp} , respectively. The rule defines the following preference:

$$\pi_j > \pi_n \quad \Rightarrow \quad W_{ijk} \text{ is prioritized over } W_{mnp}.$$

It is important to emphasize that the **Lowest Percentage Left** and **Highest Percentage Left** DRs operate at the level of individual production steps, rather than considering the overall progress of a customer order. In multi-step process chains, each step maintains its own independent production status.

For example, consider a customer order composed of two sequential steps, $O_1 \rightarrow O_2$. The percentage used in these rules reflects the completion ratio of the currently evaluated step—such as O_1 —not the cumulative progress of the full job. If O_1 has completed 60% of its required units while O_2 has not yet started, the DR computes its score based solely on the progress of O_1 .

Additionally, these rules are inherently dynamic: the computed percentages change over time as work orders are completed. As a result, the relative priorities of otherwise similar work orders may shift depending on when the decision is made.

The decision to compute progress at the step level rather than at the customer order level is motivated by the inherent complexity in evaluating global order completion in dynamic, dependency-rich environments. In many realistic scenarios, steps may have multiple predecessors and successors, including parallel and converging dependencies. For instance, if several predecessor steps partially complete their output at different times, and multiple successor steps begin consuming units in parallel, then computing a single, unified order-level completion percentage becomes not only computationally expensive but also semantically ambiguous. Step-level progress, on the other hand, is both well-defined and locally observable, making it suitable for real-time dispatching decisions at the machine level. This granularity enables machines to react precisely to the evolving state of production without requiring full visibility into the broader dependency graph of the order.

If multiple work orders remain indistinguishable in priority after the application of the DR, the machine selects first work order arriving in waiting list.

Each rule represents a distinct scheduling heuristic targeting different operational objectives, such as:

- Due-date sensitivity: Due Date, Available Date;
- Work order fairness: FIFO;
- Efficiency-oriented: Minimize Setup Time;
- Progress-aware: Total units and percentage remaining;
- Business-driven: Priority-based selection;
- Exploratory baseline: Random.

These individual rules provide a diverse basis for evaluating dispatching behavior under dynamic, decentralized shop conditions. Combined or weighted rule strategies are introduced in a subsequent section.

To illustrate how these DRs influence decision-making, consider a machine M_1 at simulation time t with a local queue containing four work orders: W_1 , W_2 , W_3 , and W_4 as shown in Table V.5. While the standard notation for a work order is W_{ijk} , indicating the step, job, and index within the step, we omit these details here for simplicity. In this example, each W_x refers abstractly to a work order, without specifying its associated step, customer order, or position within a sequence. This abstraction allows us to focus purely on dispatching logic without being tied to the hierarchical structure of the production model.

Different DRs rank these candidate work orders differently. For example, the **Due Date** rule would

work order	available	due date	created	total units	progress(%)	priority
W_1	$t - 6\text{h}$	$t + 8\text{h}$	$t - 5\text{h}$	5	60%	<i>NORMAL</i>
W_2	$t - 4\text{h}$	$t + 4\text{h}$	$t - 3\text{h}$	3	90%	<i>HIGH</i>
W_3	$t - 8\text{h}$	$t + 12\text{h}$	$t - 8\text{h}$	10	20%	<i>LOW</i>
W_4	$t - 7\text{h}$	$t + 6\text{h}$	$t - 2\text{h}$	6	30%	<i>CRITICAL</i>

Table V.5: Attributes of pending work orders in a local machine queue

prioritize W_2 , as it has the earliest due date. The **FIFO** rule would select W_3 , given its earliest creation timestamp. The **Minimize Setup Time** rule would favor W_1 , assuming that the previously processed step on machine M_1 matches the step associated with W_1 , thereby avoiding a setup. Meanwhile, the **Higher Priority First** rule would dispatch W_4 , which is marked with the highest priority level, *CRITICAL*.

The current progress of each work order’s associated step is as follows: 60% for W_1 , 90% for W_2 , 20% for W_3 , and 30% for W_4 . Accordingly, the percentage of units remaining at time t is:

$$\rho_1(t) = 40\%, \quad \rho_2(t) = 10\%, \quad \rho_3(t) = 80\%, \quad \rho_4(t) = 70\%.$$

Based on this, the **Lowest Percentage Left** rule would select W_2 for processing next.

This example demonstrates how each DR applies a distinct decision-making process to the same scheduling situation, potentially leading to significantly different outcomes.

1.3 Sequential Combination of Dispatching Rules

In practical scheduling, using a single DR often results in tied priority rankings for multiple work orders. If these ties aren’t resolved, selections become random, harming the scheduling system’s reproducibility and rationality.

Furthermore, modern manufacturing scheduling juggles multiple, competing objectives—like minimizing lead time, cutting setup costs, and prioritizing high-value orders. Relying on just one DR can throw these objectives out of balance. To fix this, sequentially combining DRs offers a structured, deterministic solution.

Sequential combination, also referred to as lexicographic prioritization, involves the ordered application of multiple dispatching criteria. The approach begins by evaluating all candidate work orders using a primary DR. If this rule yields a unique work order, the corresponding work order is selected for dispatch. However, in the case where two or more work orders are indistinguishable with respect to the primary rule, the decision process proceeds to a secondary rule, applied exclusively to the subset of tied candidates.

This hierarchical evaluation continues recursively: each rule is applied only when all preceding criteria fail to produce a unique ordering. The process terminates either when a single work order is identified or when all predefined rules have been exhausted. In the latter case, if indeterminacy still persists, a final resolution mechanism—typically random selection—may be applied, but only as a last resort.

The principal advantage of this method lies in its capacity to integrate multiple decision criteria

without requiring the explicit construction of a composite scoring function. It preserves the interpretability of each individual rule while enabling nuanced trade-offs between competing scheduling objectives. Moreover, it ensures that the scheduling process remains deterministic and reproducible, qualities that are particularly desirable in high-reliability manufacturing environments or in simulation studies aimed at comparative analysis of dispatching strategies.

Thus, sequential combination of DRs provides a logically rigorous and operationally robust solution to the tie-breaking problem, offering enhanced control over scheduling behavior and better alignment with complex production goals.

An illustrative example of sequential dispatching can be constructed using two levels of rules: **Due Date** (primary) and **Minimize Setup Time** (secondary). Consider four candidate work orders— W_1 , W_2 , W_3 , and W_4 —as shown in Table V.6.

Table V.6: Candidate Work Orders for Sequential Dispatching Example

Work Order	Due Date	Setup Time (h)
W_1	Jan 10	2
W_2	Jan 10	1
W_3	Jan 12	1
W_4	Jan 13	0.5

First, the **Due Date** rule is applied. Both W_1 and W_2 have the earliest due date (January 10), so they remain in the candidate set. W_3 and W_4 , with later deadlines, are eliminated.

Next, the **Minimize Setup Time** rule is applied to the tied candidates. W_1 requires 2 hours of setup, while W_2 only requires 1 hour. As a result, W_2 is selected for execution.

This example illustrates how sequential application of DRs can resolve tie situations deterministically, while preserving interpretability. Each rule progressively filters the candidate set using increasingly specific criteria, enabling transparent and reproducible scheduling decisions.

Sequential combination already partially address the problem of balancing objectives, by combining multiple DRs. However, this approach exhibits a fundamental structural limitation: the dominance of higher-ranked rules. Since the first rule is always applied and others are only invoked conditionally, lower-ranked rules influence the schedule only when the higher-level criteria are insufficient to discriminate among candidates. In many practical instances—particularly those involving continuous or near-continuous input domains—this results in the effective silencing of secondary criteria, leading to underutilization of potentially valuable dispatching information.

To overcome this limitation and to enable a more balanced integration of multiple objectives, we now turn to the method of weighted combination.

1.4 Weighted Combination of Dispatching Rules

Weighted combination provides a fundamentally different approach by treating all DRs as simultaneously active contributors to the decision process. Rather than imposing a rigid hierarchy, it computes a composite score for each candidate work order as a convex combination of normalized individual

rule scores. This approach ensures that all criteria influence every decision, with the extent of their influence controlled by user-defined weights.

Quantified DRs. To enable numerical comparison, each DR is modeled as a real-valued feature function defined over the set of candidate work orders \mathcal{W} . That is, each rule corresponds to a function:

$$f : \mathcal{W} \rightarrow \mathbb{R},$$

where $f(W)$ assigns a scalar score to a work order $W \in \mathcal{W}$ based on a specific scheduling criterion.

Concrete examples include:

- **Due Date :** $f_{\text{due}}(W_{ijk}) = d_j$, where d_j is the due date of job J_j associated with work order W_{ijk} .
- **FIFO:** $f_{\text{fifo}}(W_{ijk}) = \text{created}_{ijk}$, the creation timestamp of the work order.
- **Minimize Setup Time:** $f_{\text{setup}}(W_{ijk}) = \delta_{ih}$, the setup time for step O_i on machine M_h .

Note that while most dispatching features are static and time-invariant (e.g., due date, priority, creation time), some—such as **Lowest Percentage Left**—are dynamic and depend on the current simulation time t . In those cases, the feature function may be written as $f(W, t)$ to explicitly reflect this time dependency.

Dispatching feature functions $f : \mathcal{W} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ often operate on different numerical scales (e.g., hours, priority level, timestamps). In order to facilitate aggregation, they must be transformed into a common range before aggregation. This is achieved through min-max normalization, producing a normalized version $\hat{f} : \mathcal{W} \rightarrow [0, 1]$, where higher values consistently indicate more favorable scheduling decisions.

The normalization is defined as:

$$\hat{f}(W) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \max f = \min f, \\ 1 - \frac{f(W) - \min_{W' \in \mathcal{W}} f(W')}{\max_{W' \in \mathcal{W}} f(W') - \min_{W' \in \mathcal{W}} f(W')}, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

This scaling ensures three key properties:

- All scores fall within a fixed range of $[0, 1]$, enabling fair comparison and aggregation.
- The most desirable work order (i.e., one with the lowest raw feature value) receives the highest normalized score of 1.
- Features are directionally aligned, so that higher normalized values always indicate higher scheduling priority.

Special Cases. While most dispatching features follow the standard normalization scheme, two notable exceptions require separate handling:

- **Random:** The random feature assigns each work order $W \in \mathcal{W}$ a pseudo-random score $\hat{f}_{\text{random}}(W) \sim \mathcal{U}(0, 1)$. A fixed random seed is used to ensure that simulation results remain

deterministic and reproducible.

- **Higher Priority First:** Job priorities are treated as ordinal values, where lower numbers indicate higher urgency. For example:

$$CRITICAL = 1, \quad HIGH = 2, \quad NORMAL = 3$$

These raw values are then normalized using the same min-max scaling logic:

$$\hat{f}_{\text{priority}}(W) = 1 - \frac{\pi_j - \min_{W' \in \mathcal{W}} \pi_{j'}}{\max_{W' \in \mathcal{W}} \pi_{j'} - \min_{W' \in \mathcal{W}} \pi_{j'}},$$

where π_j denotes the priority of the job associated with W . This ensures that work orders from higher-priority jobs receive higher normalized scores.

- **More Total Units First** and **Highest Percentage Left:** Unlike other DRs where lower score f is prioritized, higher score f is prioritized in **More Total Units First** and **Highest Percentage Left**. Hence, the normalization in these cases is defined as:

$$\hat{f}(W) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \max f = \min f, \\ \frac{f(W) - \min_{W' \in \mathcal{W}} f(W')}{\max_{W' \in \mathcal{W}} f(W') - \min_{W' \in \mathcal{W}} f(W')}, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Once normalized, the composite score $S : \mathcal{W} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ for each work order $W \in \mathcal{W}$ is computed as a convex combination of the individual normalized scores:

$$S(W) = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \cdot \hat{f}_i(W) \quad \text{with} \quad \sum_{i=1}^n w_i = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad w_i \in [0, 1].$$

Here, each weight w_i encodes the relative importance of the corresponding normalized feature function \hat{f}_i . By adjusting these weights, the scheduling policy can be flexibly tuned to emphasize different operational goals—such as minimizing due date lateness, reducing setup time, or prioritizing high-value orders.

At each decision point, the machine selects the work order $W^* \in \mathcal{W}$ that maximizes the composite score:

$$W^* = \arg \max_{W \in \mathcal{W}} S(W).$$

This approach guarantees that scheduling decisions are both deterministic and interpretable. All specified DRs influence every decision simultaneously, and their contributions are weighted in a controlled, transparent manner. This makes the method particularly well-suited for environments with competing objectives or when reproducibility and traceability of decisions are critical.

To demonstrate the application of weighted combination in a realistic scheduling scenario, consider a case where the dispatching policy prioritizes customer orders using a weighted blend of **Due Date** and **Availability Date**. The weights assigned are 0.6 and 0.4, respectively, reflecting a stronger emphasis on timely delivery while still accounting for when an order becomes available.

In the waiting list of the machine, there are four work orders as follows:

- W_1 : Due in 12 hours, available 8 hours prior to start.
- W_2 : Due in 9 hours, available 5 hours prior.
- W_3 : Due in 7 hours, available 2 hours prior.
- W_4 : Due in 4 hours, available 10 hours prior.

Each rule is first normalized independently:

$$\hat{f}_{\text{due}}(W) = 1 - \frac{\text{due_date}(W) - \min_{W' \in \mathcal{W}} \text{due_date}(W')}{\max_{W' \in \mathcal{W}} \text{due_date}(W') - \min_{W' \in \mathcal{W}} \text{due_date}(W')}$$

$$\hat{f}_{\text{avail}}(W) = 1 - \frac{\text{available_date}(W) - \min_{W' \in \mathcal{W}} \text{available_date}(W')}{\max_{W' \in \mathcal{W}} \text{available_date}(W') - \min_{W' \in \mathcal{W}} \text{available_date}(W')}$$

The composite score for each work order is then computed as:

$$S(W) = 0.6 \cdot \hat{f}_{\text{due}}(W) + 0.4 \cdot \hat{f}_{\text{avail}}(W)$$

Table V.7: Normalized Scores and Composite Score for Each Work Order

W	$\hat{f}_{\text{due}}(W)$	$\hat{f}_{\text{avail}}(W)$	$S(W)$
W_1	0.000	0.750	0.300
W_2	0.375	0.375	0.375
W_3	0.625	0.000	0.375
W_4	1.000	1.000	1.000

As shown in Table V.7, W_4 receives the highest score of 1.0 due to having both the earliest due date and the earliest availability time. In contrast, W_1 has the lowest score (0.300), since its later due date outweighs its early availability. Interestingly, W_2 and W_3 receive identical composite scores of 0.375, but for different reasons: W_2 performs moderately well on both criteria, while W_3 has a favorable due date but poor availability.

This example highlights how weighted combination can resolve trade-offs between conflicting scheduling goals, yielding consistent and interpretable priority rankings across heterogeneous criteria.

1.5 Limitations of Dispatching Rules and Their Combinations

While DRs offer a lightweight, modular, and reactive mechanism for production scheduling, they are subject to several structural limitations inherent to their decentralized and myopic design. Each machine in the simulation operates as an autonomous agent, making scheduling decisions based solely on local information—namely, the current dispatch list and a predefined rule or combination of rules. This approach, though practical for real-time responsiveness, introduces several key drawbacks that limit its global efficiency and coordination.

First, DRs inherently lack **global system awareness**. Machines do not communicate or share scheduling state with one another. As a result, the selection of a work order by one machine is

entirely unaware of the conditions or decisions made by other machines. This can lead to suboptimal global behavior. For instance, a machine might select a work order that minimally improves its own throughput but inadvertently delays a downstream step that depends on another machine currently underutilized. In other words, locally optimal choices do not guarantee system-wide optimality.

Second, even when combining multiple DRs in a weighted or sequential manner, the **decision-making process remains locally scoped**. A machine evaluates all candidates in its dispatch list using static criteria (e.g., due date, setup time, units remaining), but it does not consider dynamic factors such as the load on other machines, expected future arrivals, or broader order dependencies. This limitation is particularly evident in cases involving complex precedence constraints, where certain scheduling decisions require global coordination to avoid bottlenecks and cascading delays.

Third, the system does not support **cross-machine negotiation** or cooperative scheduling. For example, if two machines are both capable of processing a given step, each may independently evaluate the work order based on its local state, potentially leading to non-deterministic or inefficient assignments. Furthermore, in the absence of communication, machines may unintentionally favor or neglect certain orders, exacerbating delays in multi-step production flows.

These limitations are intrinsic to the decentralized architecture implemented in this work. While DRs provide flexibility and real-time responsiveness, they are fundamentally constrained in their ability to holistically optimize schedule quality across interconnected resources. As a consequence, the schedules they produce—though feasible and responsive—are not guaranteed to be efficient in a global sense.

This motivates the inclusion of a centralized, optimization-based method such as SA, which—unlike DRs—operates with full visibility of all orders, resources, and dependencies. By comparing the output of decentralized dispatching against the globally optimized schedules produced by SA, this study aims to quantify the performance gap introduced by decentralized, non-communicative decision-making.

2 Simulated Annealing Method

To assess the performance bounds of the rule-based scheduling strategies explored in this work, we employ the metaheuristic optimization technique SA. Unlike reactive dispatching methods that make incremental, real-time decisions based on local information, SA performs a stochastic global search over the entire space of feasible schedules. It is used here solely as an **offline optimization tool**, not as a candidate for operational control.

The SA implementation begins with a complete, feasible schedule produced by a given DR. From this initial state, the algorithm iteratively explores neighboring solutions by perturbing selected assignments—specifically, by shifting a scheduled work order to a different machine and/or to a different start time, subject to feasibility constraints. Each new candidate schedule is evaluated based on a chosen performance metric (e.g., total overdue time, number of priority violations, or total setup time), and its acceptance is determined by the classical SA criterion:

$$P(\Delta E, T) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \Delta E < 0 \\ \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta E}{T}\right), & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Here, ΔE is the change in objective function value and T is the current temperature, which gradually decreases according to a cooling schedule. This mechanism allows the algorithm to escape local minima early in the search and progressively converge toward better solutions as the temperature approaches zero.

A critical precondition for the SA procedure is that the initial schedule must be **complete and feasible**. Accordingly, the simulation environment must contain no unscheduled work orders or uninitialized steps at the point of optimization. Additionally, SA assumes full and static knowledge of all customer orders, processing steps, machine capabilities, and inter-step dependencies. It is therefore fundamentally unsuitable for online scheduling, where new orders may arrive unpredictably, and machine states evolve in real time.

2.1 Neighbor selection

A fundamental component of the SA algorithm is the definition of the **neighborhood structure**—i.e., the mechanism by which new candidate solutions are generated from the current one. In this work, the neighborhood of a given schedule is defined through a single-work-order reassignment operation, where the temporal and spatial assignment of one scheduled work order is modified while maintaining the feasibility of the overall dispatching plan.

2.1.1 Dependency in Dynamic Flexible Assembly JSSP with Batch-Based execution

To be able to perform a single-work-order reassignment operation, we need to be able to determine dependency of work order and step without machine.

In the classical JSSP, determining operation dependencies is straightforward. Each job consists of a predefined sequence of operations, and each operation must be completed before the next can begin. This rigid linear structure simplifies the modeling of precedence constraints, as the dependency chain is explicitly defined and static throughout the scheduling process.

In contrast, Dynamic Flexible Assembly JSSP with Batch-Based Execution introduces significant complexity in dependency determination. Here, operations are organized around units processed in batches, and the scheduling of work orders is dynamically influenced by unit availability. Once a work order is selected for processing, it is unclear in advance which subsequent work orders will require the units it produces. This uncertainty stems from the system's flexibility and the delayed realization of dependencies until actual unit consumption occurs.

To address the challenge of ambiguous downstream dependencies, we propose a dynamic dependency resolution procedure. For each work order, its dependent work orders are defined as the latest possible work orders that require consumption of the units produced by the selected work order. In other words, among all potential consumers of a unit, we link the producing work order to the furthest one in time that still depends on those units. This design choice aims to minimize the number of reschedulings when a work order is moved later in time. By assigning dependencies only to the latest necessary consumer, the schedule avoids prematurely fixing intermediate work orders to a specific time, thereby localizing the impact of changes. When a producing work order is delayed, only its final dependent needs to be shifted, significantly reducing the overall cascade of adjustments throughout the schedule.

Figure V.6: Dependency of work order-**Example 2.1**

Figure V.7: Dependency of work order-**Example 2.2 & 2.5**

To illustrate the dynamic dependency resolution procedure and its practical implications, a series of representative examples will be presented.

Example 2.1. Consider a scenario in which a total of 10 units of step O_2 must be produced within an order. Each unit of O_2 requires one unit of O_1 as input. For the sake of simplicity, assume there is no step transition and setup time here. The work order sizes are 5 units for O_1 and 10 units for O_2 . Suppose we have a scheduling plan as illustrated in Figure V.6. In this plan, the work order W_{211} is identified as the dependent of W_{111} , since it is the one that consumes the units produced by W_{111} during its execution. Similarly, W_{211} is also dependent work order of W_{112} .

Example 2.2. Now consider a case where the work order size for O_2 is 5 units, with the scheduling plan depicted in Figure V.7. In this case, W_{212} is identified as the dependent of both W_{111} and W_{112} , as it is the latest work order that requires the units produced by these two work orders. At first glance, this may appear contradictory, since neither W_{111} nor W_{112} lists W_{211} as a dependent, despite W_{211} also consuming their output. However, it is important to note that the primary objective of this dependency assignment is not to trace the exact flow of units, but rather to guide the reassignment process during rescheduling. By focusing on the latest critical consumer, we ensure that only the most temporally sensitive dependencies influence schedule adjustments.

Figure V.8: Dependency of work order-**Example 2.3**

Figure V.9: Dependency of work order-**Example 2.4**

Example 2.3. If step O_2 can be processed on two machines while maintaining a work order size of 5 units, the resulting schedule (Figure V.8) allows two work orders to start simultaneously. In this scenario, two work orders for O_2 begin execution simultaneously. As a result, either of these work orders can be validly selected as the dependent for W_{111} and W_{112} , since both satisfy the condition of being the latest feasible consumers of the units produced.

Example 2.4. In contrast, if each step can only be processed on a single machine, the scheduling plan appears as shown in Figure V.9. In this instance, W_{211} is identified as the dependent work order of W_{111} , since the execution of W_{211} relies on the units produced by W_{111} . If W_{111} were removed or delayed, W_{211} would no longer be able to start as scheduled.

Up to this point, we have focused on cases where the targeted production quantity is exactly divisible by the work order sizes of both O_1 and O_2 . However, such ideal alignment rarely occurs in practice. When the remaining quantity does not fill an entire work order, a partial work order is used to produce exactly the units needed without exceeding the target.

Example 2.5. Suppose the work order size for O_2 is 6, and the work order size for O_1 is still 5. In this scenario, two machines are available to process O_1 , while only a single machine can process O_2 . The scheduling plan follows a structure similar to that shown in Figure V.7. Typically, the last work order of a step is the partial work order—here, this is W_{212} . In this case, W_{211} is identified as the dependent

Figure V.10: Dependency of work order-**Example 2.6**

of both W_{111} and W_{112} , since its execution depends on the units produced by them. Without either W_{111} or W_{112} , W_{211} cannot begin.

Example 2.6. Suppose now that the work order sizes for O_1 and O_2 are 5 and 4, respectively, and that each step can be processed by only one machine. The corresponding scheduling plan is illustrated in Figure V.10. We further assume that the final work order of O_2 is a partial work order, responsible for processing only 2 units. In this case, the dependent work orders of W_{111} are identified as W_{211} and W_{213} , while the dependent work orders of W_{112} are W_{212} and W_{213} .

It is worth noting that for steps without machines, dependency determination is significantly simpler. Since these steps are executed as a single block consuming all required units at once, the dependency can be assigned directly to the entire step instance. In other words, for each such step, every block of the step (i.e., the entire work order) is treated as a unified consumer. Consequently, the preceding work orders that supply the necessary units are always pinpointed as dependents of the immediately following step-without-machine execution.

2.1.2 Work Order reassignment

Work order reassignment plays a critical role in the exploration of alternative schedules within meta-heuristic search. It involves relocating a single scheduled work order to a different time or machine while preserving feasibility, honoring resource constraints, and ensuring the integrity of unit-based dependencies. The reassignment procedure consists of several tightly integrated stages:

Stage 1: Feasibility Preconditions. Reassignment is permitted only when the scheduling solution is complete—i.e., all steps are instantiated and no work orders remain unscheduled. The candidate work order must be assigned to a machine capable of processing its associated step, and its proposed new start time must not precede its created time. To avoid disrupting downstream dependencies, the algorithm restricts valid insertion points to those preceding any delayed dependent that may exist on the target machine. The candidate times are derived from the end times of scheduled work orders already present on the target machine and filtered to ensure they fall before the earliest delayed dependent. Among these, the closest eligible time not exceeding the proposed move time is selected.

To clarify the procedure for determining a valid move time during work order reassignment, consider the following example. Two customer orders, J_1 and J_2 , become available at time 00:00. J_1 requires

Figure V.11: Single work order time selection

10 units of product O_2 , while J_2 requires 10 units of product O_3 . Step O_2 has a dependency on step O_1 , whereas both O_1 and O_3 are independent and can be executed directly. All steps— O_1 , O_2 , and O_3 —have a work order size of 5 units. A single machine is available and capable of processing any of the steps, each with a uniform processing duration of 1 hour per work order.

A feasible schedule for this scenario is illustrated in Figure V.11. Suppose the selected candidate for reassignment is W_{111} . In the schedule, W_{212} is identified as a dependent of W_{111} , based on the dynamic dependency model described earlier. As a result, the candidate move times for W_{111} are constrained to lie between its created time (00:00) and the end time of W_{211} , which is 05:00. This yields a set of discrete candidate timestamps: 00:00, 01:00, 02:00, 03:00, 04:00, and 05:00. Given a proposed move time, the latest candidate time not exceeding it is selected. For instance, if the proposed time is 04:35, then 04:00 is selected as the actual move time. This ensures that no delayed dependent is violated while allowing the reassignment to occur as close as possible to the proposed time.

Stage 2: Work Order Relocation and Production Timeline Adjustment. The selected work order is removed from its current position, and its unit production record is withdrawn from the global availability timeline. Its duration is recalculated based on the work order size, machine throughput (UPH), and operation-specific success ratio. If the preceding work order on the target machine is of a different step, a setup time is applied. The work order is then reinserted at the updated start and end times, and its unit production is recorded accordingly.

Stage 3: Recursive Propagation of Followers and Dependents. Once the work order has been relocated, a three-pronged recursive propagation is initiated:

- **Followers on the same new machine:** The next scheduled work order (if any) on the same new machine is evaluated, and moved delayed in time, to make space for the the newly relocated work order. After its rescheduling, the procedure recurses on its own follower and any dependents that consume its output.
- **Dependent work orders:** All dependent work orders of the chosen work order are identified. If the new production time results in insufficient unit availability at their currently scheduled start time, these dependents are delayed to the earliest feasible point. However, they are not advanced in time during this stage—even if such a shift appears feasible.
- **Dependent steps without machines:** For dependent steps that do not require machine, feasibility is checked based on the completion of all predecessor work orders. These steps can be scheduled as soon as all required input units—across all predecessor steps—are available, including any transition times. Because they are not constrained by machine availability, they

are allowed to be scheduled immediately after the latest predecessor completes, even if that means advancing them in time relative to their previous position.

The dependent work orders are not allowed to be moved advanced in time in this stage, because of the following reasons:

- **Multiple Dependencies:** A dependent work order may require units not only from the recently moved predecessor, but also from other concurrent predecessor sources. Advancing the dependent prematurely could violate these additional dependencies, as the necessary units may not yet be available. Ensuring feasibility in such cases requires a full reevaluation of created times, which can only be done safely once all predecessor operations are settled.
- **Preservation of Logical Execution Order:** Allowing dependents to move ahead risks disrupting the intended execution order of work orders associated with the same step and customer order. Since such work orders are often organized sequentially for batching, traceability, or operational logic, violating this implicit order may introduce ambiguity or systemic inconsistency.

To avoid these complications, all dependent work orders are only allowed to move delayed in time as needed, and any potential advancement is deferred to later stage when full context is available.

Stage 4: Machine Gap Recovery and Propagation. The removal of the original work order creates a temporal gap on its former machine. To restore compactness, the next available work order is examined. If advancing this work order respects its created time and does not conflict with its predecessor, it is moved forward. Once updated, recursive propagation is applied in the same manner: adjusting followers and delaying dependents, while respecting all constraints outlined above.

Stage 5: Final Global Convergence via Created Time Recalculation. After all immediate effects of the reassignment have been addressed, the algorithm enters a convergence phase. Here, it recursively recalculates the *created time* for every scheduled work order based on the updated unit availability timelines. If a work order is found to be scheduled later than its earliest feasible start time, it is advanced accordingly. Since this phase has access to the finalized unit production and consumption history, it guarantees that all dependencies are satisfied, and all unit flows remain consistent. This final recalibration ensures that any remaining slack is removed and that no avoidable idle time remains in the schedule.

To illustrate the reassignment procedure in practice, consider the scheduling scenario depicted in Figure V.12. In this example, J_1 requires 15 units of product O_2 , while J_2 requires 15 units of product O_3 . Step O_3 depends on step O_1 , forming a sequential relationship. All steps have a uniform work order size of 5 units. Only machine M_3 is capable of processing O_3 , with a throughput of 10 UPH, whereas machines M_1 and M_2 can both process O_1 and O_2 , each with a throughput of 5 UPH. No setup time or step transition delay is considered in this example.

Suppose that work order W_{112} is reassigned from its original position to machine M_2 at time 02:00. To accommodate this move, W_{213} —originally occupying the desired slot on M_2 —must be delayed. Additionally, W_{312} , which is dependent on W_{112} , must also be postponed, as it cannot begin execution until W_{112} completes at its new position, now ending at 03:00. This delay propagates further: the new start time of W_{312} conflicts with the previously scheduled W_{313} , which must also be delayed.

Figure V.12: Example moving scenario - Initial state

Figure V.13: Example moving scenario - Intermediate result after reassignment

Meanwhile, the gap left by W_{112} on M_1 is filled by advancing W_{113} into that freed slot. The new scheduling plan is illustrated in Figure V.13.

Following the reassignment, the schedule undergoes a complete recalculation to restore feasibility and improve compactness. At 02:00, there are already 5 units of O_1 available, allowing a creation of work order of O_3 , namely W_{312} to be created with a valid created time of 02:00. Since the machine required to process O_3 is also available at that time, W_{312} can begin execution immediately. Consequently, W_{313} can also be advanced: it becomes creatable and executable from 03:00, with no dependency or resource conflicts. The fully updated schedule following the reassignment and propagation is shown in Figure V.14.

It is important to note that the dependency structure between work orders has changed as a result of the reassignment. Specifically, W_{312} is now identified as the dependent of W_{113} , while W_{313} depends on W_{112} . This adjustment reflects the reassignment’s influence on unit availability and the corresponding shift in consumption points.

2.2 Simulated Annealing

At the core of the search process lies a cost function $C(\cdot)$, which quantifies the quality of a given schedule. This function can be defined according to different scheduling objectives, such as Total overdue time across all customer orders, Total makespan of the entire schedule, or Number of priority

Figure V.14: Example moving scenario - Completed result after reassignment

violations (i.e., lower-priority orders completing before higher-priority ones). The choice of cost function determines the optimization direction and influences both acceptance decisions and the behavior of the neighbor selection mechanism.

At each iteration, the algorithm generates a neighboring solution by modifying a single work order—typically changing its start time or assigned machine. The neighbor generation strategy is informed by the cost function but kept general to allow flexibility. Once a candidate solution is obtained, its cost is compared to that of the current solution, and the change is accepted based on the classical SA rule. The high-level procedure of the algorithm is presented in Algorithm 1. The specific values for parameters such as initial solution, initial temperature, and cooling rate are not fixed here; they will be discussed in detail in the Evaluation chapter, where their impact on solution quality and convergence behavior is systematically analyzed.

The method for generating neighboring solutions is informed by the nature of the chosen cost function. For example, when minimizing total overdue time, we want work order to start as soon as possible, hence, temporal proximity and unit availability may implicitly guide how work orders are selected and reassigned. However, the design of this neighbor selection process remains flexible and is decoupled from the optimization strategy, allowing adaptation to alternative objectives.

The acceptance criterion follows the classic SA rule. Even when a new schedule has higher cost, it may be accepted with probability proportional to the Boltzmann factor $\exp(-\Delta/T)$, allowing the algorithm to escape local optima.

Termination occurs when the maximum number of iterations is reached, when no further improvement is observed after a given threshold, or when the allocated runtime budget is exhausted.

Algorithm 1 SA for Schedule Optimization

```
1: Initialize solution  $S \leftarrow$  initial schedule
2: Set temperature  $T \leftarrow T_0$ 
3: Evaluate cost  $C(S)$ 
4: Store best solution  $S^* \leftarrow S$ , best cost  $C^* \leftarrow C(S)$ 
5: for  $i = 1$  to  $maxIter$  do
6:   if termination conditions met then
7:     break
8:   end if
9:   Randomly select a neighbor  $S'$  by moving one work order
10:  Evaluate cost  $C(S')$ 
11:   $\Delta \leftarrow C(S') - C(S)$ 
12:  if  $\Delta < 0$  then
13:    Accept  $S' \leftarrow S$ 
14:  else if  $random() < \exp(-\Delta/T)$  then
15:    Accept  $S' \leftarrow S$ 
16:  else
17:    Reject change (revert to previous  $S$ )
18:  end if
19:  if  $C(S) < C^*$  then
20:    Update best solution:  $S^* \leftarrow S$ ,  $C^* \leftarrow C(S)$ 
21:    Reset stagnation counter
22:  else
23:    Increment stagnation counter
24:  end if
25:  Update temperature:  $T \leftarrow \alpha \cdot T$ 
26: end for
27: return  $S^*$ 
```

Chapter VI Evaluation

In this chapter, we evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed dispatching and scheduling methods for a dynamic, unit-aware, flexible assembly job shop system. The evaluation is designed to analyze how well different dispatching strategies and metaheuristic search techniques perform under realistic production and constraints, including machine capabilities, step dependencies, lot types, and order priorities.

1 Datasets and KPIs

Before presenting the experimental results and insights, we first introduce the datasets used for simulation and the KPIs employed for quantitative evaluation.

1.1 Datasets

Three distinct datasets are utilized for evaluation: one derived from real production data provided by an industrial partner, and two synthetically generated mock datasets designed to simulate varied scheduling scenarios.

1.1.1 Real Dataset

One of the datasets used in this evaluation is derived from a real production environment in RFID chip manufacturing. The dataset reflects a flexible assembly job shop characterized by complex product structures, heterogeneous processing capabilities, and a mixture of reusable and non-reusable lot types. The production workflow is governed by detailed BOMs, machine constraints, and customer-specific delivery requirements.

Each RFID chip production process in the real dataset consists of a structured set of manufacturing parts, each representing a logical stage in the BOM. These stages typically include wafer processing, printed role preparation, assembly, sheet cutting, and RFID chip finishing. Each part may consist of one or multiple process steps depending on the specific product variant.

For example, the wafer processing segment in the first BOM includes four steps: `bumping1`, `metallization1`, `plating1`, and `wafer_test1`. In contrast, the second BOM contains only two wafer processing steps: `metallization2` and `plating2`, omitting both bumping and explicit wafer testing. Similar structural variations occur in the printed role and sheet stages across different product configurations.

Despite sharing functional objectives—such as applying metallization to a wafer—steps like `metallization1` and `metallization2` are treated as distinct entities in the model. This differentiation accounts for

Figure VI.1: Real Data BOMs

practical constraints on the shop floor: even functionally similar steps may require independent machine setups. As setup times are non-negligible in many operations, especially in assembly and metallization, distinguishing these steps ensures that the scheduling process captures the true operational cost of switching between product-specific tasks.

The full BOM structures for the three main product families are illustrated in Figure VI.1, highlighting the hierarchical and partially parallel nature of the production flow.

Each step in the RFID production process is associated with a specific work order size (if it is step requiring machine) or a corresponding make time (if it is step requiring machine). For simplicity, Table VI.1 aggregates steps by their functional role. That is, steps such as `metallization1` and `metallization2`, which perform the same metallization function but are treated separately in scheduling due to setup requirements, are collectively listed as `metallization`. This naming convention is adopted throughout the table to focus on process characteristics rather than instance-specific identifiers.

Table VI.1: Step parameters: work order size and nominal make time

Step Name	Work Order Size (units)	Make Time (days)
assembly	50,000	–
bumping	5,000	–
lamination	55,000	–
metallization	50,000	–
wafer test	5,000	–
printing	50,000	–
sheetcutting	40,000	–
plating	–	10
test	55,000	–

The real dataset includes a heterogeneous set of machine, each mapped to specific process steps with varying throughput and setup characteristics. Machines are modeled with three core attributes: the set of step types they can process (capabilities), their processing rate in UPH, and the setup time

required when switching between distinct steps.

All machines in the real dataset are assumed to operate with a success ratio of 100%, i.e., every processed unit is completed successfully without rework or scrap. This simplification is justified by the nature of the data and allows the scheduling model to focus exclusively on throughput and timing constraints.

Table VI.2 summarizes the main machine characteristics used in the simulation model.

Table VI.2: Machine capabilities, throughput, and setup times

Machine Name	Supported Step Type	UPH	Setup Time (h)
laminator1	lamination	2000	0
laminator2	lamination	2000	0
tester1	test	2400	0
sheetcutter1	sheetcutting	10,000	0.5
assembler1	assembly	1714.3	8
assembler2	assembly	1714.3	8
assembler3	assembly	1714.3	8
assembler4	assembly	1714.3	8
assembler5	assembly	1714.3	8
assembler6	assembly	1714.3	8
assembler7	assembly	1714.3	8
assembler8	assembly	4000	8
assembler9	assembly	4000	8
assembler10	assembly	4000	8
assembler11	assembly	4000	8
metallization1	metallization	33,333	2
metallization2	metallization	33,333	2
bumper1	bumping	1000	0
printing1	printing	2000	1
waferTester1	wafer test	2000	0

Transitions between process steps are explicitly modeled in the dataset to account for inter-step delays that occur due to handling, transport, or intermediate buffering. These transitions introduce temporal dependencies between consecutive steps and directly influence the feasible scheduling windows for downstream operations.

In most cases, the transition time is zero, allowing immediate start of the successor step once its predecessor has completed. However, a select subset of transitions, particularly those involving plating or assembly outputs, incur a fixed delay of 1 day. These delays reflect realistic process lags such as third-party service handling, cooling or curing times, and post-processing logistics.

Table VI.3 lists the set of explicitly modeled transitions in the real dataset, each defined by a predecessor step, successor step, and transition duration. These constraints are used during scheduling to compute the earliest start times of dependent work orders in a temporally consistent manner.

The real dataset encompasses a comprehensive set of 25 customer orders, each with unique characteristics in terms of final product step, requested quantity, availability, due date, and priority level. These orders span a broad range of product quantities, urgency levels, and scheduling horizons, offering a diverse set of challenges suitable for evaluating scheduling methodologies under realistic conditions.

Table VI.3: Explicitly defined step transitions

From Step	To Step	Transition Time (days)
plating1	wafer_test1	1
plating2	assembly2	1
plating3	wafer_test3	1
assembly1	sheetcutting1	1
assembly2	sheetcutting2	1
assembly3	sheetcutting3	1

The priority values assigned to the orders are primarily `NORMAL`, with certain orders labeled as `HIGH` or `LOW` to explicitly test the effectiveness of priority-aware dispatching strategies. Table VI.4 presents the detailed specifications for each of these orders.

Table VI.4: Customer order specifications from the real dataset

Order ID	Final Step	Quantity	Priority	Available Date	Due Date
order0	test1	24367	<i>NORMAL</i>	2024-01-20 00:00:00	2024-06-20 00:00:00
order1	test1	87638	<i>NORMAL</i>	2024-01-31 00:00:00	2024-08-26 00:00:00
order2	test2	92667	<i>NORMAL</i>	2024-01-10 00:00:00	2024-01-18 00:00:00
order3	test1	93346	<i>NORMAL</i>	2024-01-03 00:00:00	2024-01-31 00:00:00
order4	test1	79015	<i>NORMAL</i>	2024-01-18 00:00:00	2024-06-05 00:00:00
order5	test3	22014	<i>NORMAL</i>	2024-01-12 00:00:00	2024-02-10 00:00:00
order6	test1	26835	<i>NORMAL</i>	2024-01-10 00:00:00	2024-03-11 00:00:00
order7	test3	84266	<i>NORMAL</i>	2024-01-30 00:00:00	2024-07-16 00:00:00
order8	test2	37095	<i>NORMAL</i>	2024-01-10 00:00:00	2024-05-23 00:00:00
order9	test2	26302	<i>NORMAL</i>	2024-01-30 00:00:00	2024-10-12 00:00:00
order10	test1	62739	<i>NORMAL</i>	2024-01-18 00:00:00	2024-08-07 00:00:00
order11	test3	82539	<i>NORMAL</i>	2024-01-12 00:00:00	2024-08-03 00:00:00
order12	test2	96879	<i>NORMAL</i>	2024-01-10 00:00:00	2024-03-21 00:00:00
order13	test2	91414	<i>NORMAL</i>	2024-01-19 00:00:00	2024-03-04 00:00:00
order14	test2	28475	<i>NORMAL</i>	2024-01-30 00:00:00	2024-09-17 00:00:00
order15	test2	45666	<i>LOW</i>	2024-01-10 00:00:00	2024-08-22 00:00:00
order16	test1	31147	<i>NORMAL</i>	2024-01-16 00:00:00	2024-06-03 00:00:00
order17	test3	55250	<i>NORMAL</i>	2024-01-10 00:00:00	2024-01-31 00:00:00
order18	test2	47103	<i>NORMAL</i>	2024-01-11 00:00:00	2024-04-05 00:00:00
order19	test2	85158	<i>NORMAL</i>	2024-01-31 00:00:00	2024-10-31 00:00:00
order20	test1	44451	<i>HIGH</i>	2024-01-19 00:00:00	2024-03-27 00:00:00
order21	test1	39162	<i>NORMAL</i>	2024-01-12 00:00:00	2024-07-29 00:00:00
order22	test3	38999	<i>NORMAL</i>	2024-01-12 00:00:00	2024-07-20 00:00:00
order23	test1	46510	<i>NORMAL</i>	2024-01-30 00:00:00	2024-03-28 00:00:00
order24	test1	67043	<i>HIGH</i>	2024-01-11 00:00:00	2024-04-15 00:00:00

The variety and realism embedded in these customer order parameters allow rigorous testing of DRs and metaheuristic scheduling methods, particularly with respect to key performance indicators such as adherence to due dates, priority fulfillment, and efficient resource utilization.

1.1.2 Mock Datasets

Although the real dataset offers valuable insights and realistic scheduling constraints derived directly from an industrial RFID production environment, it exhibits certain inherent limitations with respect

to generality and representativeness. Specifically, the real-world scenario features relatively homogeneous bill-of-material structures across product families, and each machine is configured with fixed capabilities tied closely to specific process steps. Such specificity restricts the ability to thoroughly evaluate scheduling methods under more diverse and complex conditions, where step configurations and machine capabilities might vary significantly.

To overcome these limitations and support a more general evaluation of scheduling strategies, two synthetic datasets—referred to as **mock datasets**—were developed and are documented in Appendix 2. These datasets are purposefully designed to meet a set of representativity criteria concerning BOM complexity, order diversity, machine flexibility, and DR responsiveness. Specifically, they include multiple overlapping BOMs, processing steps that can be performed by multiple machines (and vice versa), varied setup times and unit processing speeds, and a wide distribution of customer order parameters (e.g., priority, quantity, availability and delivery dates).

While the mock datasets may trade off some realism for generality, they enable the evaluation of scheduling strategies under more diverse and challenging conditions. Importantly, they test how algorithms perform when the decision space is less constrained and more dynamic. In the mock datasets, machines are more "capable" in the sense that they can perform multiple types of steps—not unlike flexible manufacturing systems—allowing for a broader exploration of DR effectiveness. This added generality supports stronger conclusions about rule performance under varying industrial configurations.

1.2 KPIs

To systematically evaluate scheduling performance, eight KPIs are used. These KPIs are designed to comprehensively capture scheduling efficiency, adherence to deadlines, priority compliance, and resource utilization. Specifically, the KPIs considered in this study include:

- **Number of overdue orders:** The count of orders completed beyond their specified due dates.
- **Total overdue time:** The cumulative duration by which all orders exceed their respective due dates.
- **Total priority violation:** The number of occurrences in which orders of lower priority are scheduled ahead of higher-priority orders, violating predefined priority rules.
- **Total makespan (hours):** The duration from the start of the earliest scheduled step to the end of the latest step across all scheduled orders.
- **Average make time (percentage):** The average order processing duration expressed as a percentage of the total makespan.
- **Union ratio:** A measure of resource utilization efficiency, calculated as the ratio between active processing time and the total operational time.
- **Total setup needed:** The number of setup operations required throughout the scheduling horizon.
- **Total setup time:** The cumulative duration spent performing all setup operations.

While some KPIs, such as the number of overdue orders, total overdue time, total setup needed, total setup time, and total makespan, are straightforward in their interpretation, other metrics require explicit definition to ensure clarity and reproducibility.

Total Priority Violation. A priority violation occurs when a work order of lower priority is scheduled and executed ahead of a higher-priority work order on machine capable of processing both, under specific timing conditions. To compute the total number of violations, we examine all unordered pairs of scheduled work orders (A, B) , where A has higher priority than B .

For each such pair, a violation is recorded if and only if all of the following conditions are satisfied:

1. The machine assigned to process order B is also capable of processing order A .
2. Order B starts before order A .
3. Order A is already available (i.e., its release date is earlier than the start time of order B).

If all three conditions hold, the schedule is said to violate the intended priority ordering between A and B , and one violation is added to the total count. For instance, suppose work order A (high priority) becomes available at time 1 and is scheduled after work order B (low priority), which starts at time 2 on machine that could have processed either order. This situation constitutes one priority violation.

Total priority violation is computed by applying this mechanism to every possible combination of two distinct work orders in the schedule.

Union Ratio. The union ratio is a measure of parallel processing effectiveness. It quantifies the overlap in processing times of scheduled orders, calculated as the ratio of total machine busy time (excluding overlapping durations) to the sum of individual processing times. Mathematically, it is defined as:

$$\text{Union Ratio} = \frac{\text{Total machine busy time (union of all processing intervals)}}{\text{Sum of individual processing times}}$$

For example, suppose two work orders A and B are processed on the same machine with intervals $[1, 3]$ and $[2, 4]$, respectively. The total machine busy time (union) is from 1 to 4, totaling 3 units of time, whereas the sum of their individual processing durations is 4 units. Thus, the union ratio is computed as:

$$\text{Union Ratio} = \frac{3}{4} = 0.75$$

Among the eight KPIs defined above, two metrics are of particular importance in this study: **total overdue time** and **total priority violation**. These indicators directly reflect the scheduling system's ability to respect customer due dates and maintain priority compliance—both of which are central to operational performance in high-mix, time-sensitive manufacturing environments. Minimizing total overdue time ensures that customer delivery deadlines are met, thereby maintaining service level agreements and reducing the risk of contractual penalties or loss of customer trust. Minimizing priority violations, on the other hand, reflects the system's ability to honor strategic prioritization rules,

ensuring that more critical orders receive preferential treatment in resource-constrained scenarios. Accordingly, these two KPIs serve as the primary objectives in the evaluation of DRs and metaheuristic optimization approaches throughout this study.

2 Experimental Hardware Setup

All experiments in this study were conducted on a workstation equipped with an AMD Ryzen 5 PRO 5675U processor (6 cores, 12 threads) running at 2.30 GHz. The system had 32 GB of installed RAM and ran on a 64-bit Windows 11 Business operating system with x64-based architecture. No specialized hardware acceleration (such as GPUs) was used.

3 Evaluation on Dispatching Rule Methods

In this section, we evaluate the performance of various DR-based scheduling strategies using the datasets described earlier. The objective is to examine how well different rule configurations perform under diverse production conditions, especially with respect to the two primary KPIs of interest: total overdue time and total priority violation. These rule-based approaches determine the order in which unscheduled work orders are assigned to available machines, based on criteria such as due dates, order availability, unit demand, or setup minimization.

The evaluation is conducted across both the real and mock datasets to capture performance under realistic and generalized conditions. Each rule is applied independently, and the resulting schedules are analyzed with respect to all eight KPIs, with a particular emphasis on minimizing lateness and respecting order priorities.

By systematically comparing dispatching strategies across varied production contexts, we aim to identify DRs that consistently support high delivery reliability and priority adherence—two outcomes that are critical in high-mix, deadline-sensitive manufacturing environments.

Before presenting the comparative evaluation of different DRs, we first provide a visual representation of a generated schedule using FIFO for the real dataset. This visualization offers insights into the temporal structure and resource allocation of the resulting plan, including the distribution of processing times, idle periods, and inter-step dependencies across machines. The schedule is displayed in [Figure VI.2](#).

It can be observed that these plating steps appear to overlap in the schedule, which is expected: since they do not consume shared machine resources, they can proceed concurrently. Whenever a non-machine step is instantiated, it is shown immediately in the schedule and is not subject to resource contention.

Another observation is that several machines remain idle even when other machines are actively processing work orders. This is a typical behavior under DR methods like FIFO, where machines make local decisions without global coordination. When a work order becomes available, it is assigned to the first available compatible machine. If multiple machines are idle simultaneously, the choice of machine is effectively random, which can lead to temporary underutilization of certain resources.

Finally, the visualization highlights bottlenecks in steps such as `sheetCutting` and `test`, where each

Figure VI.2: Result of real dataset using FIFO

step is served by only one machine. These resource bottlenecks naturally constrain the throughput of dependent operations, reflecting real-world challenges in production scheduling where certain specialized machines become a critical path due to limited capacity.

3.1 Evaluation on Individual Dispatching Rules

We evaluate a set of individual rule-based methods applied to the real and mock datasets. The evaluation is conducted in a controlled simulation environment where each rule is applied independently under otherwise identical conditions. This allows for an unbiased comparison of rule behavior across various production scenarios, including high machine utilization, complex dependencies, and priority-sensitive orders. All schedules are generated in a static, rule-based manner—without global optimization or post-processing—thereby highlighting the intrinsic decision-making characteristics of each dispatching strategy. The performance of each rule is measured using the eight KPIs defined earlier, with particular emphasis on minimizing total overdue time and total priority violation.

Total Overdue: Figures VI.3 and VI.4 present the number of overdue orders and the total overdue time, respectively, for each DR across all three datasets. As expected, the **Due Date** rule consistently achieves the lowest total overdue time in all datasets. This result is intuitive, as the rule is explicitly designed to prioritize work orders with earlier due dates, thus directly targeting the reduction of lateness.

Among the remaining rules, most perform comparably, with the exception of **Random** and **Highest Percentage Units Left**. The **Highest Percent Left** rule results in significantly higher overdue time. This is due to the frequent step switching it induces: as machines prioritize the step with the highest percentage of unproduced units, they tend to alternate between steps from different customer orders. As a result, individual customer orders rarely progress continuously. Instead, they are frequently interrupted and delayed, often completing only near the end of the scheduling horizon—thereby accumulating substantial overdue time.

An interesting observation is that the **Minimize Setup** rule, despite being designed to reduce overall time loss by minimizing setup operations, performs poorly in terms of overdue time. This highlights a critical trade-off: minimizing setup time does not necessarily align with minimizing delivery lateness. The rule tends to favor work orders that are similar to previous ones, which can lead to prolonged delays for dissimilar but urgent orders—ultimately harming delivery performance. Similarly, the **Available Date** rule, which prioritizes the earliest available orders, does not perform well either, likely because it ignores downstream urgency, such as due dates or priority levels.

While the KPIs **Total Overdue Time** and **Number of Overdue Orders** are naturally correlated, they are not strictly causal. A schedule with more overdue orders often results in higher total overdue time. However, exceptions exist: for example, a single severely late order can dominate the total overdue time, whereas many mildly overdue orders may have a lesser aggregate effect. In this study, we focus primarily on **Total Overdue Time** as the more informative KPI for evaluating the lateness impact of each DR.

Total Setup: The results for total setup time and total number of setups are shown in Figures VI.5 and VI.6, respectively, for all three datasets. Among all DRs, the **Minimize Setup** rule consistently yields the lowest total setup time and the fewest setup operations across all datasets. This aligns

(a) Mock dataset - 40 orders

(b) Mock dataset - 400 orders

(c) Real dataset

Figure VI.3: KPI on number of overdue orders.

(a) Mock dataset - 40 orders

(b) Mock dataset - 400 orders

(c) Real dataset

Figure VI.4: KPI on total overdue time.

directly with the rule’s objective: it prioritizes work orders that require minimal or no change in machine configuration, thereby effectively reducing setup overhead.

On the other hand, the **Highest Percentage Units Left** rule results in significantly higher setup time and setup counts. This behavior is predictable—machines that can process multiple steps are frequently forced to switch between work orders from different steps. Since each step switch incurs a setup, this leads to a high frequency of setups over time.

Another interesting observation here is that, although the **Lowest Percentage Left** rule promotes continuity by prioritizing the step with the least remaining units, it still results in high setup time and frequency. This can be attributed to its fundamentally global perspective: it aims to accelerate the completion of steps at the system level, regardless of which machine is currently processing them. As a result, at any given point in time, multiple capable machines may be assigned to process the same step of the same work order in parallel, with the goal of completing that step as quickly as possible.

The **Random** rule exhibits similarly poor performance in terms of setup efficiency. Because work orders are selected arbitrarily, there is no continuity in step assignment, leading to frequent and unnecessary setup transitions. As a result, both the total setup time and the number of setup operations increase substantially under this rule.

Figure VI.5: KPI on total setup needed.

Priority violation: The results for total priority violations across all DRs and datasets are presented in Figure VI.7. As expected, the **Higher Priority First** rule results in zero priority violations in all cases. This is by design, as the rule explicitly prioritizes work orders based on their assigned customer priority levels and thus strictly enforces the intended scheduling hierarchy.

(a) Mock dataset - 40 orders

(b) Mock dataset - 400 orders

(c) Real dataset

Figure VI.6: KPI on total setup time.

In contrast, all other DRs yield a similar and consistently non-zero number of priority violations. This is also anticipated, as these rules do not incorporate any logic related to customer order priority in their decision-making processes. Consequently, high-priority orders may be delayed in favor of lower-priority ones, leading to violations. An interesting observation is that in the real dataset, the **Due Date** rule results in a relatively low number of priority violations, although this appears to be coincidental. Since due dates and priority levels are not perfectly aligned in the dataset, the reduced violation count is likely the result of incidental overlap rather than intentional enforcement of priority constraints.

These results highlight an important practical implication: if adherence to customer-defined priorities is critical in the production environment, the scheduling strategy must explicitly include the **Higher Priority First** rule—or integrate priority-awareness more broadly into its decision logic.

Union Ratio: The results for union ratio across all DRs and datasets are presented in Figure VI.8. Overall, the union ratios achieved by different DRs are relatively similar, with only minor variations. Among them, the **Highest Percentage Left** rule exhibits a slightly higher union ratio. This behavior can be explained by the nature of the rule: it tends to focus on work orders associated with steps that have the largest remaining share of units to produce. As a result, machines are often reassigned across different steps to reduce local unit imbalances, which can lead to less temporal overlap between machines and more serialized execution. Since machines are frequently switching context rather than working in parallel on unrelated steps, the overall union of active machine time becomes more stretched across the schedule timeline, increasing the numerator in the union ratio.

(a) Mock dataset - 40 orders

(b) Mock dataset - 400 orders

(c) Real dataset

Figure VI.7: KPI on total priority violation.

(a) Mock dataset - 40 orders

(b) Mock dataset - 400 orders

(c) Real dataset

Figure VI.8: KPI on Union Ratio.

Makespan: The results for total makespan across all DRs and datasets are shown in Figure VI.9. Overall, there is no significant variation in makespan among the different rules. While one might expect that rules such as **Highest Percentage Left** and **Random**—which lead to frequent step switching and increased setup operations—would result in noticeably longer makespans, this effect is not strongly observed. Interestingly, the **Minimize Setup** rule, which is specifically designed to reduce setup overhead, does not lead to a significantly better makespan either. One possible explanation is that work orders are often distributed across machines in a way that allows for parallel processing, and that some setup overhead is effectively masked by idle periods or staggered scheduling on other machines. As a result, variations in setup behavior do not translate directly into proportional changes in the total schedule span.

Figure VI.9: KPI on Total Makespan.

Average Make Time in Percentage: The results for average make time, expressed as a percentage of the total makespan, are shown in Figure VI.10. This metric provides additional insight into how long, on average, each customer order remains in the system relative to the total scheduling horizon.

Notably, the **Highest Percentage Left** rule results in a significantly higher average make time compared to other DRs. This supports the earlier observation that under this rule, customer orders tend to progress slowly and are only completed near the end of the simulation. Because machines frequently switch between steps to address whichever has the highest remaining unit share, individual customer orders are repeatedly interrupted, causing prolonged delays in their completion. As a result, the time between the first and last operations of each order is extended, increasing the average make time relative to the overall schedule duration.

Figure VI.10: KPI on Average Make time.

An important observation from this KPI-wise evaluation is that the general behavior of DRs remains consistent across all three datasets—real and mock. Although the datasets differ in structure, complexity, and variability, the relative performance trends of each DR are largely preserved. While minor variations do occur—for example, slight differences in union ratio or make time across datasets—these deviations are expected given the inherent variability in dataset structure. However, they do not alter the overall comparative conclusions. This consistency reinforces the robustness of the observed rule behaviors and supports the generalizability of the findings beyond a single dataset instance. In summary, the evaluation demonstrates that while the specific numerical values of KPIs may vary across datasets, the qualitative performance characteristics of DRs remain stable and interpretable, offering reliable guidance for rule selection in practical scheduling scenarios.

As established earlier, this study places particular emphasis on two critical KPIs: **Total Overdue Time** and **Total Priority Violation**. In light of this, the **Due Date** and **Higher Priority First** DRs emerge as the most suitable choices for achieving these primary objectives. The **Due Date** rule effectively minimizes lateness by prioritizing work orders with earlier deadlines, while the **Higher Priority First** rule is the only method that reliably eliminates all priority violations.

The **Minimize Setup** rule also presents notable advantages, particularly in reducing both the total setup time and the number of required setup operations. However, its utility is more supportive in nature. Since setup time, while non-negligible, does not dominate the total runtime of the schedule, **Minimize Setup** is best used in conjunction with other rules that more directly address delivery or priority objectives. Hybrid strategies that combine setup efficiency with deadline or priority awareness may thus offer more balanced scheduling outcomes in practice.

3.2 Evaluation on Sequential Combinations of Dispatching Rules

In this section, we evaluate how sequential combinations of DRs perform across the same KPIs introduced earlier. We start first by evaluating the performance of sequential combinations of two DRs. The results are visualized as heatmaps for each of the eight KPIs across the three datasets. In each heatmap, the **y-axis represents the first rule in the combination**, and the **x-axis represents the second rule**. Each cell corresponds to the performance of a specific rule pair for the given KPI, with lighter colors indicating better results. KPIs results of three datasets are shown in Figure VI.11, VI.12, and VI.13. It is also important to note that the sequential combination of two identical DRs is functionally equivalent to using that rule alone. In such cases, the second rule has no additional effect, as no further tie-breaking is needed. These diagonal entries in the heatmaps (where the same rule appears on both axes) serve as a useful reference point, allowing comparison between standalone rules and their role as part of a sequence.

The results indicate that the first DR in the sequential combination has a dominant influence on the overall performance. In most cases, the choice of the first rule largely determines the behavior of the combination across KPIs. However, the second rule—used as a tie-breaker—still introduces noticeable variation within groups that share the same primary rule. The magnitude and direction of these differences vary depending on the specific KPI and the first rule applied, highlighting that while the first rule sets the overall scheduling strategy, the second rule can meaningfully refine it.

In terms of **Total Priority Violation**, all sequential rule combinations with **Higher Priority First** as the primary rule consistently result in zero violations. This outcome is expected, as the scheduling decision is first guided by priority levels. Only in cases where multiple work orders share the same priority does the secondary rule come into effect. As a result, the primary rule ensures full compliance with priority constraints, regardless of the secondary rule used.

In terms of **Total Overdue Time**, sequential combinations that use **Due Date** as the primary rule consistently result in noticeably lower overdue time compared to combinations based on other primary rules. Among these, the combination of **Due Date** followed by **Minimize Setup** achieves the lowest total overdue time overall, which aligns with expectations—orders are prioritized by urgency while still reducing unnecessary setups. However, it is worth noting that the differences among the top-performing combinations are quite subtle and not visually pronounced in the heatmaps.

Interestingly, for the KPIs **Total Priority Violation** and **Total Overdue Time**, some sequential combinations that use **Lowest Percentage Left** as the primary rule—paired with **Higher Priority First** or **Due Date** as the secondary rule—perform comparably to those where **Higher Priority First** or **Due Date** is used as the primary rule. This can be explained by the behavior of the **Lowest Percentage Left** rule, which prioritizes steps that are closer to completion. At the beginning of the schedule, when no work has yet been processed, all steps have 100% of their units remaining. In such cases, the secondary rule governs the decision, allowing the scheduler to effectively fall back on **Due Date** or **Priority**-based logic in the early stages. As the schedule progresses, the primary rule promotes continuity by favoring steps already in progress, while the initial decisions shaped by the secondary rule still contribute to timely and priority-aware order completion. This layered behavior leads to performance that is surprisingly competitive with more explicitly urgency-focused combinations.

Figure VI.11: KPIs of Sequential combination of mock dataset with 40 orders.

Figure VI.12: KPIs of Sequential combination of mock dataset with 400 orders.

Figure VI.13: KPIs of Sequential combination of real dataset.

A similar, though less pronounced, behavior is observed with the **Minimize Setup** rule when used as the primary rule in combination. Combinations such as **Minimize Setup + Due Date** or **Minimize Setup + Higher Priority First** also demonstrate reasonably good performance in **Total Overdue Time** and **Total Priority Violation**, though not as consistently as combinations based on **Lowest Percent Left**. This difference can be explained by the stronger influence that **Minimize Setup** exerts when used as the first rule. Even when a work order requiring no setup is unavailable, the rule selects the one with the minimal setup time, effectively dominating the scheduling decision and leaving less room for the secondary rule to shape the outcome. Additionally, even when multiple work orders share the same step type, they may belong to different machines. In such cases, choosing a work order of the same step does not necessarily reduce setup on the target machine, which can further reduce the effectiveness of the rule in optimizing global scheduling objectives.

As mentioned above, the influence of a DR diminishes significantly when it is placed later in the sequence. In most cases, the primary rule in a sequential combination dominates the scheduling decision, while the secondary rule only refines choices in the case of ties. As a result, the impact of any third or subsequent rule would be marginal and largely restricted to rare tie-breaking situations. Based on this, we conclude that extending the sequential combination beyond two rules offers limited additional value, and therefore focus our analysis on pairwise combinations only.

3.3 Evaluation on Weighted Combinations of Dispatching Rules

In this subsection, we investigate weighted combinations of DRs, with a particular focus on balancing multiple scheduling objectives in a more flexible and tunable manner. Given the central role of **Total Overdue Time** and **Total Priority Violation** in our evaluation, we focus on combining four DRs that are most relevant to these KPIs: **Due Date**, **Higher Priority First**, **Minimize Setup**, and **Lowest Percentage Units Left**. The goal of this analysis is to understand how adjusting the weights between these rules affects schedule quality in terms of lateness and priority compliance, and whether balanced rule combinations can outperform or match the best individual and sequential rule strategies. The evaluation is conducted across all datasets using the established KPI framework.

We begin by evaluating weighted combinations involving two individual DRs. For clarity of presentation, the weighted combination of two rules is expressed in the form:

$$S(W) = \alpha \cdot \hat{f}_{\text{firstRule}}(W) + (1 - \alpha) \cdot \hat{f}_{\text{secondRule}}(W)$$

where $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ controls the relative importance of the two rules. When $\alpha = 1$, the scheduling decision is governed entirely by the first rule; when $\alpha = 0$, only the second rule is used. Although score normalization is not applied in this formulation, this expression is intended to provide a simple and interpretable representation of the weighted aggregation mechanism.

3.3.1 Weighted Combination of Due Date and Higher Priority First

We begin by analyzing the combination of **Due Date** and **Higher Priority First**—the two DRs most directly aligned with our primary KPIs. As expected, varying the weight parameter α reveals a gradual shift in behavior: higher values of α increase the influence of the **Due Date** rule, resulting in lower total overdue time, while lower values emphasize **Higher Priority First**, leading to fewer priority violations.

Figure VI.14: Total priority violation KPI changes on weighted combination of **Due Date** and **Higher Priority First**.

In the mock datasets, this trade-off is smooth and consistent, with KPI values evolving predictably as α changes. In contrast, the real dataset exhibits less regular transitions, with some local fluctuations in KPI values. This irregularity may stem from the specific structure or limited diversity of the real dataset, and may reflect incidental interactions between rule behavior and particular work order distributions. The results of this analysis are shown in Figures VI.14 and VI.15. Depending on the specific scheduling objective—whether minimizing overdue time, reducing priority violations, or finding a compromise between the two—an appropriate value of α can be selected to achieve the desired balance.

3.3.2 Weighted Combination of Due Date and Minimize Setup

We next examine the combination of **Due Date** and **Minimize Setup**, focusing exclusively on the KPI **Total Overdue Time**, as neither rule explicitly addresses priority violations. This pairing aims to strike a balance between urgency-based scheduling and setup efficiency. The results, shown in Figure VI.16, indicate that the weighted combination yields improved performance over the **Due Date** rule alone in both mock datasets—particularly when α lies in the range of 0.80 to 0.95. In this range, the influence of setup reduction complements due-date-driven scheduling without overriding its core behavior. In the real dataset, the combined rule performs at least as well as **Due Date** alone across the same range of α . The effect, while consistent, is not strong enough to indicate a significant advantage. This suggests that while incorporating setup considerations can refine scheduling outcomes slightly, **Due Date** already captures the primary driver of overdue time in most cases, particularly when setup time does not dominate the overall schedule.

(a) Mock dataset - 40 orders

(b) Mock dataset - 400 orders

(c) Real dataset

Figure VI.15: Total overdue time KPI changes on weighted combination of **Due Date** and **Higher Priority First**.

3.3.3 Weighted Combination of Due Date and Lowest Percentage Left

We now examine the weighted combination of **Due Date** and **Lowest Percentage Units Left**, with results shown in Figure VI.17. The observed behavior is quite interesting here: the influence of **Lowest Percentage Left** diminishes almost entirely as soon as the weight α assigned to **Due Date** exceeds approximately 0.1. Beyond this threshold, the KPI values (Total Overdue Time) plateau, indicating that the scheduling decisions are driven almost exclusively by the **Due Date** component. This is especially evident in the early stages of the schedule, where most steps have not yet been processed, and their percentage of remaining units is uniformly close to 100%. As a result, the normalized scores from **Lowest Percent Left** provide little to no variation and have minimal influence on scheduling decisions. In contrast, **Due Date** scores typically span a broader and more meaningful range from the outset, reflecting real urgency differences across work orders. This gives **Due Date** a much stronger discriminative signal, even when weighted modestly. Therefore, the transition in scheduling behavior from **Lowest Percent Left** to **Due Date** occurs very early (around $\alpha = 0.1$), and the KPI trends flatten quickly thereafter.

Although weighted combinations of DRs offer a flexible way to balance different scheduling objectives, we choose not to extend the analysis to combinations involving three or more rules. Such multi-rule combinations do not offer fundamentally new insights. Their performance can often be anticipated as a weighted interpolation of known behaviors, and the complexity introduced by additional parameters does not yield proportionally deeper understanding. As such, while these combinations are certainly implementable in practice, they do not provide sufficient analytical value to justify detailed

(a) Mock dataset - 40 orders

(b) Mock dataset - 400 orders

(c) Real dataset

Figure VI.16: Total overdue time KPI changes on weighted combination of **Due Date** and **Minimize Setup**.

investigation within the scope of this study.

However, in practical scheduling environments, where multiple competing priorities may need to be considered simultaneously—such as minimizing overdue time, obeying customer priority, and reducing setup costs—a weighted combination of three or more DRs can be useful. By tuning the weights according to the specific goals or constraints of the production scenario, practitioners can achieve more tailored and balanced scheduling behavior. While such flexibility is valuable in application, a deeper analysis falls outside the scope of this study, which aims to highlight the most impactful and interpretable scheduling strategies.

3.3.4 Comparative Visualization of different Weighted Rule Combinations

To provide a more integrated view of the scheduling behavior across different rule pairings, we consolidate the total overdue time results of all three evaluated combinations into a single line chart per dataset. These plots allow for a direct visual comparison of the effects of varying α across different rule pairings and datasets.

The results are shown in [Figure VI.18](#), [Figure VI.19](#), and [Figure VI.20](#) for the mock datasets with 40 and 400 orders, and the real dataset, respectively.

Figure VI.17: Total overdue time KPI changes on weighted combination of **Due Date** and **Lowest Percentage Left**.

Figure VI.18: Comparison of total overdue time of different weighted rule combinations - Mock dataset 40 orders.

Figure VI.19: Comparison of total overdue time of different weighted rule combinations - Mock dataset 400 orders.

Figure VI.20: Comparison of total overdue time of different weighted rule combinations - Real dataset.

3.4 Summary of Dispatching Rule Evaluation

So far, we have conducted an extensive evaluation of DRs and their combinations—covering individual rules, sequential combinations, and weighted combinations—across three datasets. One of the most notable observations is the general consistency in KPI behavior across the real and mock datasets. Although numerical values may differ due to dataset-specific characteristics, the relative performance trends of DRs remain stable, indicating that the observed effects are not dataset-specific but reflect underlying rule behavior.

Each combination method offers distinct advantages. Sequential combinations enable interpretable, rule-based tie-breaking and often preserve the behavior of the primary rule, while allowing limited refinement through the secondary rule. Weighted combinations provide a more continuous and tunable mechanism for balancing multiple objectives, particularly when trade-offs between KPIs such as overdue time and priority violation are needed.

Another practical advantage of dispatching-rule-based methods lies in their computational efficiency. In all cases, the runtime for each single simulation execution remains within a practical range: approximately 2–3 seconds for the real dataset, around 5 seconds for the first mock dataset, and roughly 20 seconds for the second mock dataset. These performance levels make DR strategies well-suited for real-time or near-real-time scheduling scenarios. A simulation execution refers to one complete run of the simulation model, from the initial setup to the final state.

Beyond the evaluation presented, it is also possible to explore hybrid strategies—for instance, applying a sequential combination between two weighted rule combinations, or between a single rule and a weighted rule. These allow for more nuanced decision layers while preserving flexibility. However, applying a weighted combination of sequential rule combinations is not feasible in practice, as sequential logic is not inherently quantitative and cannot be meaningfully scored or interpolated.

Overall, the evaluation confirms that DRs and their combinations can be systematically tuned to match specific scheduling objectives, and that multi-objective rule design is both feasible and effective in diverse scheduling environments.

4 Evaluation of Simulated Annealing Method

In this section, we apply SA to the same datasets used in the DR evaluation, with performance assessed primarily using the KPI **Total Overdue Time**. While **Total Priority Violation** remains an important scheduling objective, **Total Overdue Time** is generally considered more difficult to minimize and more indicative of overall schedule quality. Therefore, the objective function in SA is defined solely to minimize total overdue time.

To evaluate the benefit of using metaheuristic search, we compare the results obtained through SA with those from the best-performing rule-based combinations. Additionally, we examine the runtime characteristics of SA to better understand the trade-off between computational cost and schedule quality.

To keep the evaluation tractable and interpretable, we focus on the real dataset and the mock dataset with 40 customer orders. The larger mock dataset containing 400 customer orders is excluded from this analysis, as it shares the same structural characteristics as the smaller one, and we expect the

scheduling behavior to remain similar. However, the significantly higher computational cost of optimizing the larger dataset—either in terms of absolute runtime or reduced number of iterations—would complicate direct comparison without yielding substantially new insights.

4.1 Cooling Rate and Termination Criteria

The cooling rate α in the SA implementation follows a geometric decay model, where the temperature is updated by multiplying it with this fixed rate after each iteration. A value of α close to 1 is chosen to allow the algorithm to perform several hundred to a thousand iterations with a sufficiently high probability of accepting worse solutions. This helps preserve the probabilistic exploration behavior over a meaningful portion of the search trajectory, thereby avoiding early convergence and preventing the algorithm from degenerating into simple hill climbing. (Note that the cooling rate α used here is unrelated to the weight parameter α employed in the weighted combination of DRs.)

Rather than fixing the initial temperature to a constant value, we dynamically initialize it as a fixed fraction of the cost of the initial solution. Specifically, the initial temperature is set as

$$T^{(0)} = \lambda \cdot C^{(0)},$$

where $T^{(0)}$ is the initial temperature, $C^{(0)}$ is the cost of the initial solution, and $\lambda \in (0, 1)$ is a constant (e.g., 0.1). This approach reflects the fact that the cost function, total overdue time, can vary widely across different problem instances, and the average cost difference between neighboring solutions is not known a priori. By scaling the initial temperature relative to the initial cost, the algorithm begins with an acceptance threshold that is roughly proportional to the problem’s scale, which helps maintain meaningful exploration dynamics regardless of dataset size.

The algorithm terminates either when the temperature decays to a negligible value or when no improvement is observed over a fixed number of iterations. Specifically, the run stops when the temperature falls below a near-zero threshold (implicitly reached after enough decay steps), or when 40 consecutive iterations yield no improvement in the best solution. This dual condition ensures that the search stops efficiently once progress stagnates, while still allowing for long enough runtime to explore meaningful regions of the solution space.

4.2 Result analysis

In each of both datasets, the analysis is conducted starting from a fixed initial solution generated using the **Random** DR. It is important to clarify that these initial schedules are not unstructured or arbitrarily generated. Rather, they are feasible solutions produced through a valid simulation process that applies the Random DR—respecting all hard constraints such as step precedence, machine capability, and setup rules.

Figures VI.21 and VI.22 illustrate the KPI progression of SA across several hyperparameter configurations for the mock and real datasets. Each run spans 10,000 iterations and takes approximately 10 minutes to complete in both real and mock datasets. The experiments vary the cooling rate and initial temperature scaling to examine the algorithm’s behavior across different exploration-exploitation balances.

As expected, SA begins with a phase of active exploration, during which it accepts worsening solutions

Figure VI.21: SA result using mock dataset.

Figure VI.22: SA result using real dataset.

with high probability. This results in a steep initial increase in the cost function (Total Overdue Time). Around iteration 1,000 to 2,000—depending on the cooling rate we choose—the temperature decays sufficiently that SA transitions into a deterministic hill-climbing phase, accepting only strictly improving moves. During this phase, further improvements become increasingly rare, and the KPI curve flattens.

Surprisingly, and in contrast to what is commonly observed in traditional JSSPs, SA does not significantly outperform dispatching-rule-based heuristics in this context. In most runs, the final solution quality remains close to that of the initial schedule, and in several cases, no improvement is achieved at all. This is particularly unexpected given that metaheuristic search methods like SA are generally designed to outperform heuristic methods by escaping local optima and exploring larger regions of the solution space - albeit with higher computational cost and much longer simulation run time.

One contributing factor to this discrepancy is the nature of the initial solutions themselves. While **Random** is considered one of the weaker DRs in terms of solution quality, it still produces schedules that are considerably better than truly arbitrary or unstructured initializations. This is evidenced by the early KPI trends in the SA runs, where performance initially worsens as the algorithm explores away from the Random schedule. The fact that this initial degradation is common across configurations suggests that even Random-based schedules lie in relatively well-formed regions of the solution space, making meaningful improvements nontrivial.

Another explanation lies in the structural characteristics of the scheduling problem. Unlike traditional JSSP, where job precedence is defined through direct task-to-task dependencies and the neighborhood can be explored through critical path swaps or local order shifts, the scheduling domain in this study includes several complicating features:

- **Multiple indirect dependencies:** A work order may rely on the availability of multiple upstream unit outputs, with no fixed schedule for their completion;
- **Unit-level dependency propagation:** Dependencies are defined at the unit level rather than the step level, introducing nonlinear feasibility constraints that are difficult to maintain during local modifications;
- **Batch-based scheduling and resource contention:** Machines operate in batch mode, meaning that rescheduling a single work order often necessitates reshuffling an entire batch sequence to preserve validity.

These constraints limit the effectiveness of local perturbations. Even with temperature-driven randomness, SA struggles to escape local regions of the solution space, and its behavior converges toward greedy search relatively early. The presence of shallow, rugged basins in the cost landscape, coupled with the limited ability of the neighborhood operator to induce meaningful structural change, prevents the algorithm from reaching higher-quality scheduling regions, such as those associated with the **Due Date** or **Higher Priority First** rules.

Moreover, although slower cooling rates and higher initial temperatures do prolong the exploratory phase, this does not translate into better final results. In some cases, excessively long exploration merely delays convergence without offering meaningful gains in schedule quality.

In summary, while SA is a theoretically powerful optimization method, its success is highly dependent on the structure of the problem and the design of the neighborhood operator. In this particular scheduling problem characterized by unit-based dependencies, batch constraints, and non-linear feasibility, standard SA methods fail to significantly improve over heuristic DRs. Conversely, DRs, though simpler, inherently respect domain-specific constraints and thus offer competitive or even superior performance, often with much lower computational cost.

Chapter VII Conclusion and Future Work

1 Conclusion

In this work, we evaluated various DR strategies and their combinations for solving a complex scheduling problem characterized by batch-based processing and unit-level dependencies. The experimental results demonstrate that DRs—especially when thoughtfully combined—are not only effective in terms of solution quality but also highly efficient in terms of runtime. This makes them particularly suitable for dynamic environments, where customer orders arrive incrementally and scheduling decisions must be made in near real time (**RQ1**).

Combinations of DRs, such as sequential or weighted strategies, can further improve scheduling outcomes by leveraging the strengths of individual DR (**RQ2**). While no single rule performs best across all objectives, targeted combinations allow the scheduling strategy to adapt to different operational goals. In particular, since the two most critical **KPIs**—**Total Overdue Time** and **Total Priority Violation**—often conflict, their trade-off must be explicitly considered. Depending on the objectives and constraints of a specific production environment, appropriate tuning of rule parameters or weighting coefficients can yield more balanced results.

To benchmark the efficiency of rule-based performances, we employed the metaheuristic optimization technique SA, which provided insight into potential gains in solution quality at the cost of increased computational effort (**RQ3**). However, the results indicate that SA did not consistently outperform the best rule-based strategies. In most cases, the initial solution—produced by a well-designed combination of DRs—was already near-optimal, and SA yielded only marginal improvements, if any. This reinforces the practical strength of carefully selected rule-based approaches in dynamic and time-sensitive scheduling environments.

As part of this study, the entire simulation environment was developed from scratch—using programming language `Kotlin` in combination with the discrete-event simulation framework `kalasim`—to provide full control over model logic, scheduling behavior, and evaluation. While off-the-shelf simulation environments or system-level infrastructures such as real-time operating system (RTOS) may offer built-in scheduling and timing mechanisms, they are not well-suited to the nature of the problem addressed here. RTOS platforms are typically designed for hard real-time constraints in embedded or control systems, where task execution must be guaranteed within strict deadlines (e.g., milliseconds). In contrast, the scheduling problem studied here involves soft timing constraints, large-scale data dependencies, and dynamic order arrivals—requiring flexible, high-level decision-making. Therefore, a customized, extensible simulation architecture was necessary to support the complexity and

experimental needs of this work.

This study also introduced a tailored simulation framework designed to model the dynamics of batch-based scheduling with unit-level dependencies and soft timing constraints. The simulation environment was crafted to provide full transparency and control over the scheduling mechanism, enabling systematic evaluation of DRs under realistic production conditions.

Beyond its use for experimentation, the framework conceptually serves as a foundation for developing a **digital twin** of the production system. A digital twin, in this context, would maintain a live, synchronized representation of the manufacturing environment by integrating real-time data from the shop floor. Such a system could continuously evaluate scheduling decisions, anticipate bottlenecks, simulate alternative strategies, and assist planners in responding to disruptions or changing priorities. With growing digitization in manufacturing, this type of decision-support capability represents a crucial step toward more adaptive and resilient scheduling systems.

2 Future Work

The DRs explored in this work are inherently *machine-centered*—that is, each machine makes scheduling decisions based solely on its local waiting list, without awareness of the state or queue of other machines. While this decentralized decision-making ensures simplicity and scalability, it can also lead to suboptimal global outcomes due to lack of coordination. A natural first step toward improvement is to shift toward a *job-centered* perspective, where each work order can evaluate and choose among eligible machines based on factors like expected completion time, setup costs, or current load. Combining machine- and job-centered logic could further enhance the scheduling strategy by introducing a degree of global awareness while preserving the strengths of local decision-making.

Although DRs offer a robust and lightweight approach, there remains significant potential for enhancing solution quality through more advanced methods. One promising direction is the use of hybrid techniques that combine heuristic and metaheuristic elements. For instance, one could perturb a portion of the schedule—by moving a selected work order or time window—and then use DRs to re-optimize only the affected parts. This could produce more meaningful neighborhood structures for metaheuristic search while preserving scalability and feasibility.

Another promising research direction, which addresses the static nature of DR methods, is the use of AI to adapt rule selection or parameterization based on the current system state. Rather than replacing rule-based logic, AI methods could operate at a meta-level—selecting or weighting DRs based on contextual factors such as order backlog characteristics, bottleneck formation, or shifting production priorities. For example, reinforcement learning could be used to learn policies that dynamically choose between rule combinations (e.g., FIFO + Minimize Setup vs. Highest Priority First) depending on KPI trade-offs observed during the current scheduling horizon. Such a system would not generate schedules from scratch but instead guide the dispatching strategy in real time, improving responsiveness to unexpected disruptions or load imbalances. In contrast to static rule configurations, this would enable a form of adaptive control that remains interpretable and feasible by design.

Furthermore, this AI-guided approach opens the door to *machine- and time-specific rule selection*, where different dispatching policies can be dynamically applied to different equipment types or production periods. For example, machines with high setup costs might prioritize rule sets that minimize

tool changes, while heavily loaded machines could switch to throughput-maximizing strategies. During peak demand periods, urgency-based rules might be favored over fairness-driven ones. This localized adaptability could significantly enhance the robustness and flexibility of rule-based scheduling without compromising transparency. Ultimately, this approach could serve as a foundation for intelligent scheduling assistants that retain the clarity of heuristic methods while benefiting from AI-guided adaptability.

Another avenue for future exploration is the application of exact or constraint-based optimization techniques, such as Constraint Programming or Mixed Integer Linear Programming. These methods have the potential to produce near-optimal or optimal solutions, particularly in semi-dynamic environments where more information is available in advance. However, they also come with higher computational costs and may require richer problem formulations, which could limit their practicality in real-time scenarios.

A further area worth exploring is the application of declarative optimization techniques, particularly multi-shot Answer Set Programming (ASP). Unlike procedural or mathematical formulations, ASP enables scheduling constraints and rules to be specified in a purely declarative manner, which supports compact and transparent encoding of precedence, exclusivity, and resource logic. The multi-shot solving paradigm allows the system to incrementally react to new customer orders or state changes without restarting from scratch—making it highly suitable for dynamic scheduling scenarios.

One limitation of ASP, however, is its lack of native support for continuous time modeling. This can be mitigated by discretizing the time domain into fixed intervals (e.g., hourly slots), transforming the problem into a time-indexed logic formulation that remains solvable by the ASP engine. While discretization may reduce temporal granularity, it enables logical inference over complex scheduling dependencies with high flexibility. As such, ASP may complement heuristic or metaheuristic methods in situations where logical constraints are dominant and frequent re-optimization is required.

In summary, while this study establishes the strong baseline performance of DR strategies, further improvements may be achieved by developing more sophisticated hybrid or constraint-aware models—especially when extended to environments with more predictable scheduling horizons.

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Chapter A Appendix

1 AI Use Declaration

To ensure transparency and uphold academic integrity, the following table outlines the AI tools utilized during the preparation of this report. This declaration aligns with TU Dresden’s guidelines on the responsible use of AI in scientific writing.

Table A.1: AI Use Declaration

AI-Based Tool	Use Case	Scope	Remarks
ChatGPT 4.0 Last access: 20.06.2025	Text generation	Entire work	Used across multiple threads for drafting and clarification.

2 Mock datasets

This section documents the synthetic mock dataset containing 40 customer orders, which is used throughout the evaluation to study scheduling behavior under general and flexible conditions. The dataset is designed to reflect realistic variability in customer requirements, including differences in order quantity, product type (final step), availability date, due date, and priority level. The dataset includes a diverse set of steps, multiple overlapping BOMs, and flexible machine configurations to support a broad and representative scheduling environment.

The full lists of steps, machine capabilities, customer orders, step transition are shown bellow:

Due to space constraints, mock dataset of 400 customer orders are not shown here. The full dataset follows the same structural and statistical properties as the 40-order mock dataset, with extended volume and order variability to test algorithm scalability. The complete data is available on Zenodo at [32].

Table A.2: Step parameters: work order size and nominal make time (mock dataset)

Step Name	Work Order Size (units)	Make Time (days)
step1	1000	–
step2	–	4
step3	600	–
step4	700	–
step5	1500	–
step6	800	–
step7	800	–
step8	800	–
step9	900	–
step10	1000	–
step11	750	–
step12	850	–
step13	800	–
step14	820	–
step15	840	–

Table A.3: Machine capabilities, throughput, and setup times (mock dataset)

Machine Name	Supported Step Type	UPH	Setup Time (h)
eqn1	step1	62	8.0
eqn1	step5	50	9.6
eqn2	step4	50	8.0
eqn2	step6	45	4.0
eqn2	step7	60	–
eqn2	step9	50	2.0
eqn2	step10	50	3.0
eqn2	step12	47	2.5
eqn2	step13	60	2.0
eqn3	step3	60	–
eqn3	step4	45	2.0
eqn3	step8	50	4.0
eqn3	step11	50	2.4
eqn3	step12	50	2.0
eqn3	step15	55	2.0
eqn4	step9	55	1.5
eqn4	step13	50	1.0
eqn4	step14	50	2.0

Table A.4: Explicitly defined step transitions (mock dataset)

From Step	To Step	Transition Time (days)
step1	step2	0.5
step2	step4	0.33
step5	step6	0.67
step9	step13	1.00
step13	step15	0.5
step2	step3	0.17
step3	step12	0.5
step2	step12	0.33

Table A.5: Customer order specifications (mock dataset)

Order ID	Final Step	Quantity	Priority	Available Date	Due Date
order1	step7	8848	<i>NORMAL</i>	2024-01-18	2024-03-16
order2	step4	6376	<i>NORMAL</i>	2024-01-25	2024-05-09
order3	step15	3826	<i>NORMAL</i>	2024-01-18	2024-06-13
order4	step7	3355	<i>CRITIC</i>	2024-01-20	2024-03-06
order5	step12	4618	<i>CRITIC</i>	2024-01-18	2024-04-27
order6	step4	2866	<i>LOW</i>	2024-02-16	2024-04-12
order7	step15	8371	<i>NORMAL</i>	2024-01-12	2024-04-17
order8	step13	2589	<i>VERY LOW</i>	2024-01-08	2024-03-10
order9	step7	5701	<i>NORMAL</i>	2024-02-12	2024-07-20
order10	step6	3887	<i>CRITIC</i>	2024-01-19	2024-05-24
order11	step6	3074	<i>CRITIC</i>	2024-01-08	2024-03-14
order12	step4	1226	<i>VERY LOW</i>	2024-02-15	2024-04-16
order13	step12	9571	<i>CRITIC</i>	2024-01-12	2024-04-21
order14	step15	8803	<i>NORMAL</i>	2024-01-21	2024-02-23
order15	step15	3664	<i>HIGH</i>	2024-01-29	2024-02-05
order16	step4	3360	<i>HIGH</i>	2024-01-12	2024-03-12
order17	step7	7287	<i>LOW</i>	2024-01-24	2024-03-14
order18	step13	4682	<i>HIGH</i>	2024-01-11	2024-03-01
order19	step13	7820	<i>CRITIC</i>	2024-01-20	2024-04-10
order20	step15	1220	<i>NORMAL</i>	2024-01-23	2024-03-17
order21	step12	7585	<i>VERY LOW</i>	2024-01-02	2024-04-07
order22	step4	1441	<i>CRITIC</i>	2024-01-12	2024-02-27
order23	step13	7398	<i>LOW</i>	2024-02-06	2024-03-21
order24	step13	8782	<i>NORMAL</i>	2024-02-01	2024-03-30
order25	step15	7581	<i>HIGH</i>	2024-01-22	2024-03-21
order26	step4	8190	<i>VERY LOW</i>	2024-02-10	2024-04-17
order27	step7	1057	<i>NORMAL</i>	2024-02-01	2024-03-13
order28	step7	1385	<i>HIGH</i>	2024-01-03	2024-07-11
order29	step13	6492	<i>NORMAL</i>	2024-01-21	2024-05-17
order30	step13	3676	<i>NORMAL</i>	2024-02-16	2024-03-19
order31	step13	7087	<i>HIGH</i>	2024-01-04	2024-01-12
order32	step7	8703	<i>LOW</i>	2024-02-07	2024-05-12
order33	step4	6106	<i>VERY LOW</i>	2024-02-12	2024-07-26
order34	step15	4698	<i>HIGH</i>	2024-01-19	2024-05-14
order35	step7	2981	<i>HIGH</i>	2024-01-04	2024-01-18
order36	step15	4445	<i>CRITIC</i>	2024-02-15	2024-05-20
order37	step13	3496	<i>LOW</i>	2024-01-22	2024-06-20
order38	step12	6584	<i>CRITIC</i>	2024-01-21	2024-07-26
order39	step12	7755	<i>CRITIC</i>	2024-02-02	2024-06-22
order40	step12	9291	<i>LOW</i>	2024-01-12	2024-07-12